

1 **Single-Atom Coordinated MXenes for Organic Pollutant**
2 **Detoxification: Mechanistic Insights, Challenges, and Future**
3 **Directions**

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32 **Abstract**

33 Organic pollutants, including plastics, pharmaceuticals, aromatic compounds, pesticides, and
34 industrial solvents, pose a serious threat to soil quality, aquatic ecosystems, and human health. Single-
35 atom-coordinated MXenes (SAs@MXenes) have emerged as promising platforms for detoxifying
36 organic pollutants because of their tunable surface chemistry, high catalytic activity, and atomic-level
37 precision. Anchoring isolated metal atoms on the MXene surface maximizes atom utilization and
38 modulates the electronic structure, thereby improving charge separation, adsorption affinity, and
39 redox reactivity. However, comprehensive reviews of this emerging class of SAs@MXenes catalysts
40 for organic pollutant detoxification remain limited. This review summarizes diverse synthesis
41 strategies for achieving stable single-atom dispersion, including defect engineering to anchor single
42 atoms at vacancy sites, heteroatom coordination chemistry, axial coordination, the modulation of local
43 electronic structure through ligand control, and UV-mediated synthesis that enables photochemical
44 precision in atom placement. In addition, advanced characterization techniques are used to confirm
45 atomic dispersion, oxidation states, and structural evolution, while electron paramagnetic resonance
46 (EPR) spectroscopy provides insight into the reactive intermediates responsible for detoxification.
47 Furthermore, SAs@MXenes functions as both an efficient catalyst and a robust adsorbent for the
48 degradation and capture of organic contaminants. Computational approaches, including density
49 functional theory (DFT), machine learning (ML), and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, are
50 emphasized to elucidate catalytic mechanisms, accelerate catalytic design, and clarify molecular-level
51 interactions. Collectively, these strategies support the rational development of single-atom-
52 coordinated MXenes for sustainable environmental detoxification, and their future perspectives are
53 also presented.

54 **Keywords:** Single atoms, MXenes, Organic pollutants, Detoxification, Density functional theory

55 **1. Introduction**

56 The increasing presence of organic pollutants in aquatic environments, particularly antibiotics,
57 pesticides, endocrine-disrupting compounds, and other emerging contaminants, has become a
58 pressing global concern [1-3]. Pharmaceutical agents such as sulfamethoxazole, sulfadimidine,
59 acetaminophen, carbamazepine, and ranitidine are extensively used for therapeutic purposes but
60 exhibit high persistence, low biodegradability, and strong bioactivity [4,5]. Their continuous
61 release into water systems contributes to severe environmental and health risks, including
62 antibiotic resistance, endocrine disruption, liver and kidney toxicity, neurological effects, and
63 reproductive impairments. These contaminants also accumulate in aquatic organisms, causing
64 oxidative stress, reproductive toxicity, and bioaccumulation across algae, invertebrates, and fish
65 [6-10].

66 Conventional nanomaterial-based catalysts, including nanoparticles and nanoclusters, have
67 several limitations in treating pharmaceutical pollutants. Only surface atoms participate in
68 catalysis, where the majority remain inaccessible, resulting in low atomic utilization and reduced
69 catalytic efficiency [11-13]. Active sites tend to be heterogeneous and poorly defined, complicating
70 the control of electronic structure and adsorption behavior toward complex drug molecules. These
71 catalysts frequently trigger non-selective radical pathways ($\cdot\text{OH}$, $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$), which may lead to
72 incomplete degradation and the formation of toxic intermediates rather than full mineralization
73 [14-16]. Additionally, particle agglomeration under reaction conditions decreases stability and
74 necessitates higher catalyst dosages, while the potential for metal leaching poses risks of secondary
75 contamination.

76 Emerging single-atom catalysts (SACs), composed of isolated metal atoms dispersed on
77 supports, offer 100% atomic utilization, high catalytic efficiency at low metal loading, and reduced

78 material cost [17-19]. They combine the advantages of homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis,
79 offering reusability, structural tunability, and high selectivity. These emerging SACs cover
80 catalysis, electrochemical energy conversion and storage, and sensor technologies [20-23].
81 However, due to their high surface free energy, individual metal atoms tend to migrate and
82 aggregate into nanoclusters unless adequately stabilized [24-28]. Preventing aggregation requires
83 anchoring isolated metal atoms to chemically active sites on suitable supports, thereby enhancing
84 stability and promoting strong electronic interactions and charge transfer between the anchored
85 atoms and the substrate [29-32]. A variety of substrates, including metal oxides, metal-organic
86 frameworks (MOFs), molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂), and graphene-based materials, have been
87 investigated for stabilizing single atoms [33-36]. Among these, two-dimensional (2D) materials
88 are particularly promising because they offer ultrahigh specific surface areas, tunable surface
89 functionalities, and abundant anchoring sites for atomic dispersion [37,38]. MXenes, a class of 2D
90 transition-metal carbides, nitrides, and carbonitrides with the general formula M_{n+1}X_nT_x, (where
91 M is a transition metal, X is carbon and/or nitrogen, and T_x represents surface terminations such
92 as -O, -OH, or -F), have emerged as exceptional supports for SACs [39,40]. Their high surface
93 energy, adjustable electronic configuration, uniform atomic lattice, and rich surface functional
94 groups enable the efficient capture and subsequent stabilization of metal cations as isolated atoms
95 [41-43].

96 Moreover, the synthesis of MXenes typically involves an etching process that selectively
97 removes specific metallic elements from the parent MAX phase. During this process, certain
98 transition-metal atoms within the MXene lattice are inevitably dissolved, creating structural
99 vacancies or defect sites [44-46]. These vacancies possess unsaturated coordination environments
100 and intrinsic reducibility, forming highly active centers that can simultaneously adsorb and reduce

101 metal cations in situ. Consequently, single metal atoms can be stabilized through a simple one-step
102 anchoring mechanism. SAs@MXenes have attracted increasing attention because of their unique
103 two-dimensional layered structure, hydrophilicity, tunable surface terminations, and high
104 electronic conductivity, which enable diverse chemical interactions with organic pollutants,
105 including electrostatic attraction, hydrogen bonding, π - π stacking, and redox reactions [47-50].
106 When decorated with single-atom catalytic sites, MXenes not only adsorb pharmaceutical
107 molecules but also activate advanced oxidation processes (AOPs), generating reactive oxygen
108 species (ROS) such as $\cdot\text{OH}$, $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$, and $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$. These radicals effectively degrade antibiotics and
109 pharmaceuticals into smaller, less toxic intermediates, which are ultimately mineralized into CO_2
110 and H_2O . This synergistic adsorption-catalysis mechanism enhances catalytic efficiency,
111 selectivity, and stability, thereby positioning MXene-based materials as promising candidates for
112 the sustainable remediation of pharmaceutical pollutants in aquatic environments [51-54].

113 The integration of DFT, ML, and MD simulations has become essential for advancing the
114 rational design and mechanistic understanding of single-atom-coordinated MXenes
115 (SAs@MXenes) in environmental detoxification. **Schemes 1a** and **b** illustrate the timeline of
116 SAs@MXenes development for organic pollutant detoxification. DFT-based mechanistic studies
117 provide atomic-level insights into electronic structures, adsorption energies, and reaction
118 pathways, enabling the identification of active sites and catalytic mechanisms [55]. The specialized
119 and emerging nature of MXenes, SACs, and ML applications for the degradation of organic
120 pollutants is reflected in the limited number of studies that address their intersection. ML tools in
121 materials science, particularly those predicting catalytic performance, remain in an early stage of
122 development. Consequently, the integration of ML with SAs@MXenes for the degradation of
123 specific pollutants represents a frontier in current research [56-58].

124 Meanwhile, MD simulations provide a complementary dynamic perspective by capturing real-
125 time molecular interactions, diffusion, and adsorption mechanisms during detoxification processes
126 [59]. This review summarizes recent advances in the synthesis strategies, coordination chemistry,
127 and mechanistic insights of SAs@MXenes for treating organic contaminants. Additionally, the
128 interplay between surface terminations, vacancy engineering, and atomic coordination is explored
129 to elucidate their collective influence on catalytic reactivity and stability. Finally, key challenges
130 and future perspectives are presented, emphasizing the potential of SAs@MXenes as a
131 transformative platform for sustainable environmental remediation. The selected organic
132 compounds and their toxic effects are summarized in Table 1.

133

134 *1.1.Scope of the review*

135 Recent review articles focus on MXene-based composites, including MXene-conjugated polymer
136 nanoarchitectures and MXene-based hybrid composites such as MXene@MOF, MXene@g-C₃N₄,
137 MXene@metal oxides, and MXene@quantum dots, with a major emphasis on applications in
138 batteries, electrochemical energy storage, photocatalytic energy conversion, and general pollutant
139 degradation [60-62]. In addition, a recent review addresses SAs@MXenes for electrochemical
140 applications. Notably, none of the previously published reviews comprehensively addresses
141 SAs@MXenes for organic pollutant detoxification [63].

142 This review comprehensively examines the potential of SAs@MXenes as catalysts and adsorbents
143 for addressing the growing challenges posed by organic molecular contaminants in water systems.
144 The widespread use of antibiotics, analgesics, hormones, and other pharmaceuticals has resulted
145 in their persistent presence and incomplete removal in conventional wastewater treatment plants,
146 raising significant environmental and health concerns. In this context, MXenes, a new class of

147 two-dimensional transition metal carbides and nitrides, exhibit unique physicochemical properties,
148 including high surface area, tunable surface terminations, and excellent conductivity, making them
149 promising substrates for stabilizing isolated single-atom active sites. Synthesis strategies,
150 including vacancy engineering, heteroatom coordination, and surface-termination modification,
151 enable SAs@MXenes catalysts to strongly anchor single atoms and precisely control their local
152 coordination environments. These structural features not only improve atomic utilization but also
153 regulate the d-orbital electronic structure and modulate charge-transfer processes, thereby
154 promoting highly efficient catalytic activity for treating toxic organic molecules. Particular
155 attention is devoted to the chemistry underlying pollutant removal, encompassing adsorption
156 interactions such as electrostatic attraction, π - π stacking, and hydrogen bonding, as well as
157 advanced oxidation mechanisms mediated by single-atom sites. These catalytic sites can
158 selectively activate oxidants, including peroxymonosulfate (PMS), peroxydisulfate (PDS),
159 hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), and oxygen (O_2), to generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) or
160 facilitate non-radical pathways that degrade complex pharmaceutical structures. Finally, this
161 review outlines future research directions, including the rational design of SAs@MXenes guided
162 by density functional theory (DFT), the integration of machine learning (ML) approaches with
163 hybrid treatment processes, and field-scale validation for real wastewater applications. The
164 conceptual overview of this review is illustrated schematically in **Scheme 2**.

165

166 **2. Importance of the SAs@MXene catalyst**

167 SAs@MXenes catalysts have gained significant attention in recent years because of their unique
168 combination of atomic-level precision, electronic tunability, and superior catalytic performance
169 [64-66]. The integration of SAs@MXenes substrates bridges the gap between heterogeneous and
170 homogeneous catalysis, allowing precise control over the active-site structures and reaction

171 mechanisms. In conventional nanoparticle-based catalysts, only surface atoms participate in
172 catalytic reactions, leaving most atoms buried and inactive. In contrast, SAs anchored on MXenes
173 achieve complete atomic utilization because each atom is individually dispersed and fully
174 accessible for the reaction [67,68]. This approach maximizes the efficiency of expensive noble
175 metals and enables high catalytic activity with minimal metal loading. The uniform dispersion of
176 SAs across the MXene surface creates a homogeneous catalytic environment, minimizing site
177 heterogeneity and enhancing the predictability of performance. A major challenge in the design of
178 SACs is preventing atom aggregation. MXenes offer a chemically active, defect-rich surface with
179 numerous anchoring sites, including -O, -F, -OH, and -Cl terminations, as well as exposed Ti, V,
180 or Mo atoms. These reactive sites form strong metal-support bonds via M-X-M coordination
181 (where M denotes a single atom), thereby stabilizing the isolated atoms and preventing migration
182 or sintering even under harsh reaction conditions. This strong interfacial bonding also modifies the
183 metal center's d-band structure, thereby tuning its catalytic reactivity and selectivity [69-72].
184 MXenes possess metallic conductivity and highly tunable surface chemistry, which can be tailored
185 through composition (e.g., $Ti_3C_2T_x$, Mo_2CT_x , Nb_2CT_x , and V_2CT_x) and surface functionalization.
186 When single atoms are anchored, charge transfer occurs between the metal atom and the MXene
187 substrate, optimizing the electronic configurations at the active site. Consequently, SAs@MXenes
188 systems exhibit exceptional versatility in pollutant oxidation and reduction processes due to their
189 enhanced redox activity [73]. Importantly, these systems serve as ideal model platforms for
190 investigating fundamental catalytic mechanisms at the atomic scale [74, 75]. The well-defined
191 coordination structures of SAs on the MXene surface allow detailed experimental and theoretical
192 exploration of structure-property-activity relationships, yielding valuable insights for the rational
193 design of next-generation catalysts. Overall, SAs@MXenes systems combine atomic efficiency,

194 electronic tunability, and structural stability, making them highly promising candidates for
195 advanced catalytic applications.

196

197 **3. Various strategies for the synthesis of SAs@MXenes catalysts**

198 The synthesis of SAs@MXenes has attracted considerable research interest because of its potential
199 to maximize atomic efficiency, modulate electronic structures, and enhance catalytic performance.

200 To achieve well-defined coordination environments and prevent metal aggregation, a range of
201 synthetic strategies has been developed.

202 Defect engineering is one of the most widely employed approaches, in which intrinsic or
203 induced vacancies on the MXene surface serve as anchoring sites for single atoms, thereby
204 promoting strong metal-support interactions. Heteroatom coordination chemistry involves
205 heteroatoms such as nitrogen, sulfur, or phosphorus that form stable coordination bonds with single
206 atoms, thereby stabilizing them within the MXene lattice. Axial coordination strategies provide
207 further control over the local electronic environment by introducing ligands or surface groups
208 along the vertical axis, thereby regulating the activity and selectivity of catalytic sites. UV-
209 mediated synthesis has also emerged as a green and efficient method that promotes metal precursor
210 reduction and uniform dispersion under mild conditions, reducing energy requirements and
211 minimizing aggregation. Beyond these techniques, other emerging methods, such as
212 electrochemical deposition, atomic layer deposition (ALD), and in situ growth, offer
213 complementary routes for achieving precise atomic dispersion and scalable fabrication of
214 SAs@MXenes catalysts.

215

216 *3.1. Defect engineering*

217 The $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ surface, which naturally contains -O, -OH, and -F terminations after MAX phase
218 etching, undergoes rapid thermal shock treatment in a hydrogen atmosphere. This high-
219 temperature process eliminates surface oxygen-containing groups, generating oxygen vacancies
220 that act as active sites [76]. When platinum (Pt) precursors are introduced, these vacant oxygen
221 sites serve as strong anchoring centers, where isolated Pt atoms are immobilized through the
222 formation of Pt-Ti bonds. This process ensures atomic-level Pt dispersion without nanoparticle
223 aggregation (Fig. 1(a)). The resulting Pt SAs, which are uniformly distributed on $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$, provide
224 highly active catalytic sites and substantially enhance catalytic performance [77]. S. Park et al.
225 reported the stabilization of single Pt atoms within vanadium vacancies of V_2CT_x MXene. The
226 V_2AlC MAX phase was etched with hydrofluoric acid (HF) to remove aluminum layers, yielding
227 V_2CT_x MXene sheets with terminal functional groups. During etching and delamination, vanadium
228 vacancies (V-vacancies) were naturally generated, producing highly unstable, reductive defect
229 sites that can trap foreign atoms. Upon the addition of H_2PtCl_6 solution, $[\text{PtCl}_6]^{2-}$ ions were
230 adsorbed onto the MXene surface. The reductive environment of the V-vacancies promoted a self-
231 reduction process in which Pt ions were reduced and confined directly within the vacancy sites
232 (Fig. 1(b)). Once immobilized, each Pt atom bonded with three neighboring carbon atoms (Pt-C)
233 and interacted with oxygen terminations (Pt-O), forming a stable coordination environment.
234 Furthermore, the V metal atom vacancy and its role in SAs@MXenes catalysts are described by
235 S. Park and coworkers [78]. The structural and microscopic characterization confirms the
236 formation of vacancies in Pt- V_2CT_x . (Fig. 2(a-e)) illustrates how TEM/HAADF-STEM images
237 and EDS mapping analysis are combined to demonstrate that the atoms are rearranged in the Pt-
238 V_2CT_x lattice after synthesis. Fig. 2d clearly shows that the lattice distortions indicate the presence
239 of V vacancies, which create unsaturated coordination sites to accommodate the guest Pt SAs. Fig.

240 2e shows the high-intensity profile of a single atom, as marked in the HAADT-STEM image in
241 Fig. 2b. These defect sites are crucial because they can accommodate active atoms, which enhance
242 electron redistribution and increase the number of catalytically active sites. (Fig. 2(f-h)) illustrates
243 the molecular structural models of MXenes with V-O vacancies and Pt SAs chelation, and
244 correlates these vacancy defects with enhanced catalytic performance. Vacancies modify the
245 electronic structure of the catalyst surface, facilitating faster electron transfer and stronger
246 interactions with pollutants or reactants. Consequently, catalytic degradation or conversion
247 efficiency improves compared with defect-free materials [78].

248

249 3.2. Heteroatom coordination

250 Heteroatoms such as N, S, P, and B introduced onto the MXene surface can create strong metal-
251 support interactions, thereby stabilizing isolated SAs, modulating the d-band center, and improving
252 the catalyst's charge-transfer efficiency. The synthesis of the Ru single-atom anchored nitrogen-
253 doped $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ ($\text{Ru}_{\text{SA-N-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x}$) catalyst follows a coordination-assisted route comprising three
254 main steps: etching, coordination, and thermal stabilization. First, $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene was prepared
255 by etching the Al layers from Ti_3AlC_2 using a LiF/HCl solution to obtain few-layer nanosheets.
256 Subsequently, the resulting MXene suspension was mixed with melamine, which acted as a
257 nitrogen source, and RuCl_3 , which provided Ru(III) ions that coordinated with the nitrogen atoms
258 of melamine. The mixture was freeze-dried and subsequently annealed at 550 °C under argon
259 atmosphere, during which nitrogen atoms were doped into the MXene framework and isolated Ru
260 atoms were anchored to these N sites via strong Ru-N bonds. This coordination strategy effectively
261 prevented Ru aggregation and ensured atomic-level dispersion [80]. P. Yang et al. reported the
262 incorporation of heteroatoms with varying electronegativities, such as boron (B), phosphorus (P),

263 sulfur (S), and nitrogen (N), into the coordination environment of single-atom Cu sites on MXene
264 supports *via* a one-step calcination method. These heteroatoms partially replaced oxygen atoms in
265 the Cu-O₃ moiety, creating new asymmetric coordination structures such as Cu-O₂B. During
266 synthesis, boric acid and copper chloride precursors were co-calcined with Ti₃C₂T_x MXene, where
267 the negatively charged oxygen terminations and surface functional groups of the MXene stabilized
268 the Cu atoms and enabled substitution by B atoms (Fig. 3(a)). The introduced heteroatom entered
269 the first coordination shell of the Cu atom, redistributing the local electron density and modulating
270 its valence state. This electronic modulation altered the charge-transfer process between Cu active
271 sites and peroxymonosulfate (PMS), rendering the Cu centers more electron-deficient and thereby
272 enhancing their selectivity toward the adsorption of terminal oxygen atoms in PMS [81].

273 Furthermore, the Ru single-atom-doped MXene catalyst (Ru_{SA}-N-S-Ti₃C₂T_x) was synthesized
274 by selectively etching Al layers from the Ti₃AlC₂ MAX phase using a LiF/HCl mixture to yield
275 few-layer Ti₃C₂T_x MXene with abundant -O and -OH groups. These functional groups served as
276 anchoring sites for Ru³⁺ ions when MXene was mixed with RuCl₃.xH₂O and thiourea. A freeze-
277 drying step prevented nanosheet restacking and promoted uniform distribution of Ru. Subsequent
278 annealing at 500 °C under an inert atmosphere induced thiourea carbonization, incorporated N and
279 S dopant, and stabilized atomically dispersed Ru through Ru-N and Ru-S coordination bonds (Fig.
280 3(b)). The dual doping of N and S was crucial for preventing Ru aggregation while simultaneously
281 tuning the electronic environments of both Ru atoms and the MXene support [82].

282

283 3.3. Axial coordination

284 The Co_{SA}-N₂O₁/MXene catalyst was synthesized using an axial coordination strategy. In this
285 approach, single-layer Ti₃C₂T_x MXene nanosheets with abundant -O and -OH surface terminations

286 were first prepared and then combined with a $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and dicyandiamide (DCD) solution to
287 anchor cobalt precursors onto the MXene surface. After freeze-drying, the precursor was subjected
288 to pyrolysis, during which cobalt atoms were fixed in a single-atom state coordinated by two in-
289 plane nitrogen atoms (from DCD-derived carbon nitride) and one axial oxygen atom (from MXene
290 terminations), forming a $\text{Co-N}_2\text{O}_1$ configuration. The introduction of this axial oxygen ligand
291 disrupted the symmetry of the conventional Co-N_4 structure and generated an electron-deficient
292 Co center (Fig. 1(c)), thereby enabling selective peroxymonosulfate activation to produce singlet
293 oxygen with high efficiency [83]. Y. Dai et al. synthesized the Alk-MXene/FePc catalyst through
294 a self-assembly route. Ti_3AlC_2 was first etched to form $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene and then alkalized to
295 introduce $-\text{OH}$ terminations, producing Alk-MXene with a crinkled 3D framework. Subsequent
296 ultrasonic self-assembly with Fe-phthalocyanine (FePc) yielded a hybrid structure in which Fe
297 atoms were uniformly dispersed on the Alk-MXene support, exhibiting an $\text{Fe-N}_4\text{O}_1$ coordination
298 environment. This synthesis not only produced a stable 2D/3D composite but also introduced an
299 additional axial Fe-O bond from the MXene support, distorting the Fe-N_4 square-planar geometry
300 into a quasi-octahedral $\text{Fe-N}_4\text{O}_1$ configuration (Fig. 3(c)). The axial ligand mechanism plays a
301 crucial role in tuning the electronic structure of the Fe center, as axial O coordination modifies the
302 crystal field and reduces spin polarization by redistributing electrons among the d_{z^2} , d_{xz} , and
303 d_{yz} orbitals. This electronic rearrangement decreases the number of unpaired electrons and induces
304 a low-spin state [84].

305

306 *3.4. UV-mediated synthesis*

307 Co single atoms anchored on MXene substrates were synthesized using an ice-assisted
308 photochemical reduction method. Initially, MAX phase precursors (V_2AlC , Nb_2AlC , and Ti_3AlC_2)

309 were prepared, after which frozen CoCl_2 ice cubes were added to MXene dispersions and
310 maintained at $0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to enable the gradual release of Co^{2+} ions, thereby preventing nanoparticle
311 formation (Fig. 4(a)). Upon UV irradiation (254 nm, 10 W), the Co^{2+} ions were photochemically
312 reduced and anchored as single Co atoms onto oxygen-terminated MXene surfaces via Co-O
313 coordination bonds. This process produced uniformly dispersed Co atoms without aggregation.
314 The strong Co $3d - \text{O } 2p$ hybridization in $\text{Co}@V_2\text{CTx}$ facilitated electron transfer between Co and
315 the MXene substrate, thereby improving catalytic activity [85].

316 The surface of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene was first modified with L-tryptophan molecules through a
317 nucleophilic substitution and dehydration reaction between the $-\text{COOH}$ groups of L-tryptophan
318 and the surface $-\text{OH}$ terminations of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$. This modification formed Ti-O-C linkages,
319 introducing Lewis-basic nitrogen sites that acted as anchoring and chelating centers for metal ions.
320 In the subsequent step, aqueous solutions of CoCl_2 and NiCl_2 were frozen into ice cubes and added
321 to the Try- $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ dispersion, which was then irradiated with UV light (254 nm) at $0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2
322 hours. Under UV irradiation, photons induced the reduction of Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions, producing
323 reactive metal species that were immediately chelated by nitrogen and oxygen atoms on the Try-
324 $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ surface (Fig. 4(b)). This photochemical reduction proceeded under mild conditions,
325 preventing aggregation and enabling the formation of atomically dispersed Co and Ni atoms, some
326 of which paired as dual Co-Ni atomic sites. The UV light provided the necessary activation energy
327 for electron transfer, thereby facilitating the controlled in situ reduction and anchoring of metal
328 atoms through Co-N, Co-O, Ni-N, and Ni-O bonds [86].

329

330 *3.5. Other methods*

331 A newly prepared Pt-Nb₂C single-atom catalyst (Fig. 4(c)) demonstrates the stepwise
332 transformation from the Nb₂AlC MAX phase to Pt-anchored Nb₂C MXene. Initially, Nb₂AlC was
333 etched in an HF solution to remove the Al layers, producing few-layer Nb₂C nanosheets with
334 abundant vacancy sites and surface functional groups. These sites served as active anchoring
335 centers for Pt ions derived from H₂PtCl₆, which were subsequently adsorbed onto the Nb₂C
336 surface. Subsequently, the mixture was annealed under a H₂/Ar atmosphere, reducing Pt⁶⁺ to
337 metallic Pt atoms that became uniformly anchored within Nb vacancies. The resulting Pt-Nb₂C
338 nanoplateform contained atomically dispersed Pt sites stabilized through strong Pt-Nb coordination
339 and electronic interactions [87]. Furthermore, J. Zhang et al. reported the synthesis of Mo₂TiC₂T_x-
340 Pt_{SA} via simultaneous electrochemical exfoliation and single-atom immobilization. In this
341 approach, Mo₂TiC₂T_x MXene, obtained by HF etching of Mo₂TiAlC₂, was subjected to potential
342 cycling in an acidic electrolyte using a Pt foil counter electrode. During potential cycling, protons
343 interact with oxygen-terminated Mo sites, generating Mo-OH and Mo-OH₂ intermediates that
344 weaken Mo-C bonds and promote Mo atom dissolution, thereby forming Mo vacancies. These
345 vacancies acted as anchoring sites, while Pt atoms dissolved from the Pt foil migrated and became
346 trapped within the vacancies through strong Pt-C and Pt-O covalent bonds. Hydrogen evolution
347 during cycling facilitated exfoliation into few-layer nanosheets with enlarged interlayer spacing,
348 increasing the number of accessible active sites for atomic Pt dispersion [88]. The Ru single-atom
349 anchored Ti₃C₂T_x MXene (Ru_{SA}@Ti₃C₂T_x) was synthesized using a wet-chemistry impregnation
350 method, wherein exfoliated MXene rich in oxygen-containing functional groups and surface
351 vacancies served as an ideal substrate for atomic dispersion. Ti₃C₂T_x was first prepared by selective
352 etching of the MAX phase using a LiF-HCl solution, followed by ultrasonic exfoliation to produce
353 few-layer nanosheets with abundant -O and -OH terminations. Subsequently, a RuCl₃ solution was

354 added to the MXene suspension, allowing Ru^{3+} ions to anchor to oxygen-terminated sites via
355 strong Ru-O coordination interactions. Prolonged stirring ensured a uniform ion distribution and
356 prevented aggregation, resulting in atomically dispersed Ru sites stabilized by surface defects.
357 Finally, the composite was separated, washed, and freeze-dried to yield $\text{Ru}_{\text{SA}}@\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ with well-
358 defined Ru-O coordination [89]. The synthesis of various SAs@MXene composites is summarized
359 in Table 2. Furthermore, MXene can accommodate both single atoms and nanoclusters. Z. Sun et
360 al. show that a $\text{Ni}_x@\text{Mo}_2\text{TiAlC}_2$ catalyst is prepared by an impregnation method, where Ni atoms
361 are dispersed between the MXene layers (Fig. 5(a)), and the depth-molecular profile of $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiAlC}_2$
362 (MTAC) is shown in (Fig. 5(e)). The layered MTAC MXene structure provides abundant metal-
363 support interaction sites, enabling Ni atoms and nanoclusters anchor strongly. The MTAC structure
364 ensures that, even in the presence of Ni atoms and nanoclusters, the phase remains unchanged,
365 indicating that MTAC supports structural stability during catalyst preparation (Fig. 5(b-d)). At low
366 Ni loading (0.5Ni/MTAC), HAADF-STEM images show mainly isolated bright dots,
367 corresponding to Ni single atoms, which are stabilized through strong interaction with Mo/Ti sites
368 of the MXene lattice (Fig. 5(f)). The interaction traps Ni atoms, preventing migration and
369 aggregation, thereby achieving excellent atomic utilization. In contrast, at high loading
370 (1.5Ni/MTAC), Ni mainly forms nanoclusters, which are larger and more prone to sintering. The
371 intermediate loading (1Ni/MTAC) exhibits the coexistence of single atoms and nanoclusters, with
372 isolated Ni atoms and small clusters appearing simultaneously (Fig. 5(g-i)). Whereas Fig. 5j-n
373 shows the STEM-EDS mapping and confirms the presence of Ni, Mo, Ti, and Al moieties. The
374 synthesis strategy provides both highly active single-atom sites and cluster sites on the MTAC
375 MXene support, thereby facilitating dual reaction steps, including bioethanol activation and
376 dehydrogenation. This synthesis strategy opens a new avenue for MXene to accommodate dual-

377 atom, multi-atom, and cluster configurations, expanding its applications across various fields,
378 including catalysis, energy conversion, storage, organic molecules, and gas sensing [90]. In
379 addition, Table 3 compares various synthesis strategies and their advantages for producing large-
380 scale catalysts. Among these methods, wet chemistry, impregnation, and pyrolysis are scalable,
381 according to the data.

382

383 **4. Advanced characterization techniques**

384 SAs@MXenes represent a frontier in materials science due to their exceptional atomic utilization,
385 tunable coordination environments, and superior catalytic activity compared with conventional
386 nanostructured catalysts. The atomically dispersed metal centers anchored on MXene surfaces
387 provide well-defined active sites, while MXene's abundant surface functionalities and high
388 electrical conductivity promote rapid electron transfer and enhanced structural stability. However,
389 the precise identification and understanding of the local structure, oxidation states, and
390 coordination chemistry of these single atoms remain challenging, requiring advanced
391 characterization techniques.

392 High-Angle Annular Dark-Field Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (HAADF-
393 STEM) enables the direct visualization of single atoms on MXene substrates with atomic
394 resolution and Z-contrast, confirming their dispersion and spatial distribution. Complementary
395 techniques, such as X-ray Absorption Near Edge Structure (XANES) and Extended X-ray
396 Absorption Fine Structure (EXAFS), provide quantitative information on oxidation states,
397 coordination numbers, and local atomic environments, thereby establishing clear structure-activity
398 relationships. Raman spectroscopy further aids in probing the vibrational modes of MXene lattices,
399 defect states, and surface terminations that influence the stability of atom anchoring and electronic

400 interactions. Collectively, these advanced techniques offer a multidimensional understanding of
401 SAs@MXenes systems, linking atomic-level structure to catalytic performance. Such insights are
402 essential for the rational design of SAs@MXenes for applications in energy conversion,
403 environmental remediation, and molecular separation.

404

405 *4.1. HAADF-STEM analysis*

406 High-Angle Annular Dark-Field Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (HAADF-STEM)
407 is one of the most effective methods for directly characterizing SAs@MXenes. Due to its Z-
408 contrast imaging capability. HAADF-STEM clearly distinguishes individual heavy-metal atoms
409 dispersed on lighter MXene substrates, enabling unambiguous confirmation of single-atom
410 dispersion without aggregation into clusters or nanoparticles. This technique provides atomic-
411 resolution images of the MXene lattice and reveals the spatial distribution, anchoring sites, and
412 coordination environments of isolated atoms. In SAs@MXenes, HAADF-STEM has been
413 particularly valuable for identifying preferential binding at surface defects, vacancies, or functional
414 terminations, thereby correlating structural configurations of active sites with catalytic
415 performance.

416 Aberration-corrected HAADF-STEM imaging provides direct evidence of atomically
417 dispersed metal sites on MXene supports. The bright single spots correspond to isolated Co atoms
418 anchored on $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$, appearing brighter than C or Ti due to the higher atomic number of Co. This
419 confirms the existence of atomically dispersed Co single-atoms rather than clusters or
420 nanoparticles. The anchoring occurs through coordination with surface -O, -OH, and -C functional
421 groups of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ [92]. Fig. 6 illustrates the detailed morphological and structural characterization
422 of the $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ -Pt_{SA} catalyst. TEM images of pristine $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ (Fig. 6(a)) and $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ -Pt_{SA} (Fig.

423 6(c)) reveal ultrathin, transparent nanosheets with smooth surfaces that remain intact after Pt
424 incorporation and calcination. The corresponding SAED pattern (Fig. 6(b)) confirms a well-
425 ordered hexagonal crystal structure with high crystallinity. The HRTEM image (Fig. 6(d)) shows
426 distinct lattice fringes with an interplanar spacing of 2.6 Å, corresponding to the (100) plane of
427 $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$, indicating that Pt loading preserved the structural integrity of the MXene. The simulated
428 atomic model of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x\text{-Pt}_{\text{SA}}$ (Fig. 6(e)) supports the uniform dispersion of single Pt atoms on the
429 MXene surface. The aberration-corrected HAADF-STEM image (Fig. 6(f)) displays bright spots,
430 highlighted by red circles, representing atomically dispersed Pt atoms uniformly distributed on
431 $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$. No aggregation or nanoparticle formation was observed, confirming atomic-level
432 dispersion. HAADF-STEM-EDS elemental mapping (Fig. 6(g)) demonstrates the homogeneous
433 distribution of Ti, C, O, and Pt, verifying the successful incorporation of Pt atoms [77].

434 Z. Lei et al. reported that Ti vacancies and low-valence Ti sites with strong reducing ability are
435 generated on Ti_3CNT_x during etching. Upon introducing $\text{H}_2\text{PtCl}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, these Ti species
436 spontaneously reduce Pt^{4+} ions. At low precursor concentrations, the reduced Pt atoms are
437 individually trapped within Ti vacancies, whereas at higher concentrations, the limited number of
438 vacancies leads to the formation of stable sub-nanometer Pt clusters alongside isolated atoms [93].
439 Similarly, W. Chen et al. investigated the atomic structure of MXene-like $\text{Ni}_1/\text{TiC}_{0.5}\text{N}_{0.5}$ using
440 aberration-corrected HAADF-STEM. Bright atomic spots corresponding to Ni atoms were
441 uniformly dispersed across the $\text{TiC}_{0.5}\text{N}_{0.5}$ matrix. Due to Z-contrast, these spots were attributed to
442 Ni single atoms substituting titanium (Ti) sites within the lattice, suggesting that Ni atoms are
443 doped into the crystal structure and adopt a coordination environment similar to Ti atoms in
444 $\text{TiC}_{0.5}\text{N}_{0.5}$ [94]. (Fig. 7(a)) presents the HAADF-STEM image of the $\text{Co}_{\text{SA}}\text{-N}_2\text{O}_1/\text{MXene}$ catalyst,
445 showing bright atomic spots corresponding to isolated Co atoms uniformly dispersed on the

446 MXene nanosheets. The yellow circles mark individual Co atoms, confirming the successful
447 formation of a SAC structure rather than Co clusters or nanoparticles. The measured interatomic
448 distance between two adjacent Co atoms (~ 0.322 nm) supports atomic-level separation and stable
449 anchoring on the MXene substrate. The EDS elemental mapping (Fig. 7(d)) revealed homogeneous
450 distributions of Co, Ti, N, O, and C, indicating the successful in-situ growth of Co single atoms on
451 the MXene framework [83]. In (Fig. 7(b)), the HAADF-STEM images of Cu-SA/MXene and Cu-
452 SA/B-MXene-4 show bright dots representing isolated Cu atoms uniformly anchored on MXene
453 nanosheets without aggregation, confirming the presence of well-dispersed single-atom sites. In
454 Cu-SA/B-MXene-4 (Fig. 7(c)), the Cu atoms are more densely and evenly distributed due to boron
455 doping, which provides additional coordination sites and enhances metal-support interactions. The
456 bright spots correspond to Cu atoms stabilized via Cu-O₂B coordination [81]. The AC HAADF-
457 STEM image of Pd₁-Ti₃C₂T_x also reveals bright spots, highlighted by yellow circles,
458 corresponding to atomically dispersed Pd atoms on the Ti₃C₂T_x surface (Fig. 7(e)) [95].

459 The HAADF-STEM image (Fig. 8(a)) shows the Ti_{3-x}C₂T_y MXene nanosheets exhibiting clear
460 lattice fringes corresponding to the (013), (018), and (0012) planes, confirming their crystalline
461 structure. The bright dots in the image correspond to isolated Pt atoms embedded within the Ti<sub>3-
462 x</sub>C₂T_y lattice. As shown in (Fig. 8(b)), these Pt atoms are uniformly distributed and occupy Ti
463 vacancy sites rather than interstitial positions, indicating substitutional doping. The intensity
464 profile (Fig. 8(c)) further distinguishes Pt atoms from Ti and C columns by their higher atomic
465 number, appearing as bright spots. The comparison between the experimental and simulated
466 HAADF-STEM images (Fig. 8(d)) confirms that Pt atoms replace surface Ti atoms and are
467 stabilized within vacancy sites through strong Pt-C bonding. This configuration validates the
468 formation of a genuine single-atom catalyst in which each Pt atom is individually anchored and

469 coordinated by surrounding carbon atoms within the MXene lattice. The HAADF-STEM images
470 and elemental mappings (Fig. 8(e-g)) further demonstrate the successful synthesis of $\text{Ru}_1/\text{Ti}_{3-x}\text{C}_2\text{T}_y$,
471 $\text{Ir}_1/\text{Ti}_{3-x}\text{C}_2\text{T}_y$, $\text{Rh}_1/\text{Ti}_{3-x}\text{C}_2\text{T}_y$, and $\text{Pd}_1/\text{Ti}_{3-x}\text{C}_2\text{T}_y$. In all cases, bright atomic dots correspond
472 to isolated single metal atoms uniformly distributed on the MXene surface without visible
473 aggregation or nanoparticle formation. Elemental mapping confirms the homogeneous
474 distributions of Ti (red) and the respective metals (green), indicating that each metal atom is
475 confined within Ti vacancy sites through metal-carbon coordination. These results demonstrate
476 that the self-reduction and stabilization mechanism employed for Pt can be effectively extended to
477 other noble and transition metals [96].

478

479 *4.2. XANES and EXAFS analysis*

480 X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) is a powerful element-specific technique that provides
481 detailed insight into the local environment and electronic structure of complex materials. It consists
482 of two complementary regions: X-ray Absorption Near Edge Structure (XANES) and Extended
483 X-ray Absorption Fine Structure (EXAFS). XANES, located within ~ 50 eV of the absorption edge,
484 is highly sensitive to oxidation states, coordination geometry, and unoccupied electronic states of
485 the absorbing atom, making it valuable for probing electronic structures and chemical bonding.
486 EXAFS, extending hundreds of eV beyond the edge, arises from the interference between the
487 outgoing photoelectron waves and those scattered by neighboring atoms. It provides quantitative
488 information, such as bond lengths, coordination numbers, and local disorder. XANES qualitatively
489 reveals the oxidation and coordination environment, whereas EXAFS enables precise structural
490 determination. Together, these methods offer a comprehensive understanding of both the electronic
491 and atomic structures of catalysts. For MXenes, which are characterized by high conductivity,

492 surface terminations, and tunable defect sites, XAS serves as an essential tool for correlating
493 atomic-scale structure with catalytic function, thereby guiding the rational design of efficient
494 MXene-supported single-atom catalysts.

495 The Co K-edge XANES spectrum of Co-Ti₃C₂T_x displays a white-line peak between those of
496 metallic Co foil (Co⁰) and CoO (Co²⁺), indicating that the Co species possess an intermediate
497 valence state. This suggests partial charge transfer from Ti₃C₂T_x to Co atoms, stabilizing Co in a
498 mixed-valence configuration that prevents aggregation and maintains high catalytic activity. The
499 FT-EXAFS spectrum of Co-Ti₃C₂T_x shows no Co-Co peak but exhibits a main peak at ~1.61 Å,
500 corresponding to Co-O coordination. The absence of Co-Co interactions indicates that Co atoms
501 are isolated rather than forming metallic clusters. Instead, they are coordinated with O and C atoms
502 in the MXene framework, which act as strong anchoring sites to prevent atomic migration or
503 sintering. EXAFS fitting results reveal coordination numbers of ~1.0 for Co-C at 1.81 Å and ~5.0
504 Co-O at 2.05 Å. These findings confirm that each Co atom is stabilized within a Co-C₁O₅
505 coordination environment on the Ti₃C₂T_x support. The O and C terminations of MXene function
506 as robust anchoring points, enabling the formation of atomically dispersed Co single-atom
507 catalysts (SACs) [92].

508 The normalized XANES spectra at the Pt L₃-edge for Pt foil, Pt-MXene-10, and Pt-MXene-
509 12.5 show that the white-line intensity of PT-MXene catalysts is stronger than that of metallic Pt
510 foil, indicating that Pt atoms in these systems possess partial positive charges resulting from
511 electronic interactions with the MXene support. Notably, Pt-MXene-10 exhibits a higher white-
512 line intensity than Pt-MXene-12.5, suggesting that Pt in the single-atom form has a higher
513 oxidation state and more balanced electron density around the Pt sites. The FT-EXAFS spectrum
514 of Pt-MXene-10 displays a dominant peak at ~1.5 Å, corresponding to Pt-N/C/O coordination,

515 confirming that single Pt atoms are stabilized through bonding with MXene surface terminations.
516 A weaker secondary peak at ~ 2.5 Å indicates a small fraction of Pt-Pt interactions, suggesting
517 minor clustering even at low metal loading. In contrast, Pt-MXene-12.5 shows a pronounced peak
518 at ~ 2.2 Å, indicating stronger Pt-Pt contributions associated with the formation of sub-nanometer
519 Pt clusters, along with a weaker low-R peak (~ 1.25 Å) originating from residual Pt-N/C/O bonds
520 due to the presence of a small number of single atoms [93]. W. Chen et al. reported that the
521 normalized Ti K-edge XANES spectra for Ni₁/Ti_{0.5}N_{0.5} exhibit a higher rising-edge position than
522 Ti foil, indicating a cationic Ti state resulting from electron transfer from Ti to neighboring N and
523 C atoms. The R-space of Fourier-transformed EXAFS spectra at the Ti K-edge reveals the presence
524 of Ti-N/C-Ti coordination shells, consistent with the crystalline structure of TiC_{0.5}N_{0.5}. The Ni K-
525 edge XANES spectra for Ni₁/TiC_{0.5}N_{0.5} display a rising-edge position located between that of Ni
526 foil and NiO, suggesting that Ni atoms possess an oxidation state between Ni(0) and Ni²⁺. The R-
527 space FT-EXAFS spectra at the Ni K-edge show two distinct peaks at approximately 1.69 Å and
528 2.22 Å, corresponding to Ni-N/C and Ni-Ni coordination, respectively. Quantitative EXAFS curve
529 fitting for the Ni-N/C path yields an average coordination number (CN) of 4.6 and a bond distance
530 of 2.09 Å, similar to the Ti-N/C bond length in TiC_{0.5}N_{0.5}. For the Ni-Ni path, the CN is estimated
531 to be only 1.1, significantly lower than in bulk Ni, indicating that only a few Ni clusters coexist
532 with single atoms. Furthermore, Wavelet transform (WT) analysis of Ni K-edge EXAFS
533 oscillations provides enhanced radial distance resolution. The WT contour plot for Ni/TiC_{0.5}N_{0.5}
534 exhibits maximum intensities at ~ 8 Å⁻¹ for Ni-Ni coordination and 4 Å⁻¹ for Ni-N/C coordination,
535 further confirming the coexistence of both coordination types in the material [94]. The atomic
536 structure and electronic state of Cu single atoms in Cu_SA/MXene-4 were analyzed through XPS
537 and XAS by P. Yang et al. The B 1s XPS spectrum (Fig. 9(a)) confirms the incorporation of B

538 atoms into the MXene lattice, forming Ti-B and Ti-B-O bonds. The Cu 2p XPS spectra (Fig. 9(b))
539 show that both samples contain mixed Cu(0)/Cu(I) and Cu(II) species, with Cu_{SA}/B-MXene-4
540 exhibiting a higher Cu valence, indicating electron withdrawal by neighbouring B atoms. The
541 XANES spectra (Fig. 9(c)) support this observation, as a positive edge shift reflects an increase in
542 the Cu oxidation state upon B doping. The EXAFS spectra (Fig. 9(d-f)) reveal that the Cu atoms
543 are atomically dispersed with no Cu-Cu bonds, confirming a single-atom configuration. The fitting
544 results demonstrate that Cu in Cu-SA/MXene is coordinated by three oxygen atoms (Cu-O₃), while
545 Cu in Cu_{SA}/B-MXene-4 adopts a Cu-O₂B coordination, where B substitutes one atom in the local
546 environment. The wavelet transform (Fig. 9(g)) shows a shift toward lower R values in Cu_{SA}/B-
547 MXene-4, confirming Cu-B/O coordination [81].

548 The normalized Co K-edge XANES spectra (Fig. 10(a)) show that the absorption edge position
549 of Co_{SA}-N₂O₁/MXene lies between those of Co foil and CoO, indicating that the Co atoms are in
550 an intermediate oxidation state. The oxidation states of Co_{SA}-N₄ and Co_{SA}-N₂O₁/MXene (Fig.
551 10(b)) reveal that the latter exhibits a slightly higher valence, which is attributed to the electron-
552 withdrawing effect of the axial oxygen ligand. The Fourier-transformed EXAFS spectra in R-space
553 (Fig. 10(c,d)) display a dominant Co-N/O coordination peak near 1.5 Å and no Co-Co scattering
554 peak, confirming the atomic dispersion of Co atoms. The wavelet-transform (WT-EXAFS) contour
555 plots (Fig. 10(e)) further distinguish Co-N/O coordination from Co-Co interactions, where only
556 the Co-N/O signal is observed, reaffirming the absence of Co aggregation. The fitted EXAFS curve
557 of Co_{SA}-N₂O₁/MXene (Fig. 10(f)) aligns closely with the experimental data, verifying the presence
558 of a CoN₂O₁ coordination environment. The optimized DFT-derived atomic model (Fig. 10(g))
559 illustrates a single Co atom anchored on the MXene surface with two nitrogen atoms in the basal
560 plane and one oxygen atom in the axial position, confirming the CoN₂O₁ structure [83].

561 In the EXAFS spectrum of Pd₁-Ti₃C₂T_x (Fig. 11(a)), two main peaks are observed at 1.78 Å
562 (Pd-O) and 2.48 Å (Pd-Ti), while no Pd-Pd coordination peak is detected, confirming the absence
563 of Pd nanoparticles and validating the isolated single-atom state. The EXAFS fitting curves (Fig.
564 11(b)) reveal coordination numbers of ~3.5 for Pd-O and ~1.5 for Pd-Ti, indicating that oxygen
565 atoms play a dominant role in stabilizing Pd single atoms. These results provide clear evidence
566 that Pd atoms are atomically anchored and stabilized through Pd-O and Pd-Ti bonding. The Pd K-
567 edge XANES spectra (Fig. 11(c)) show that the absorption edge of Pd₁-Ti₃C₂T_x lies between that
568 of Pd foil (metallic Pd) and PdO (Pd²⁺), suggesting that Pd atoms in the MXene matrix possess an
569 intermediate oxidation state (0 < Pd < +2). The WT Analysis (Fig. 11(d)) displays only Pd-O and
570 Pd-Ti features, again confirming single-atom dispersion without the formation of metallic Pd
571 clusters [95].

572

573 4.3. Raman spectroscopy analysis

574 Raman spectroscopy is a powerful vibrational technique widely used to investigate the structural
575 and surface properties of MXene-based single-atom systems. For MXenes, Raman spectra provide
576 valuable information on lattice vibrations, surface terminations, and defect states, all of which are
577 highly sensitive to the incorporation of single atoms. The introduction of isolated metal atoms onto
578 MXene surfaces often results in subtle shifts of characteristic Raman peaks, variations in intensity
579 ratios, or the appearance of new modes, indicating changes in bonding interactions, strain effects,
580 and local electronic environments. These spectral modifications help differentiate pristine
581 MXenes, functionalized surfaces, and single-atom-anchored structures. Furthermore, the non-
582 destructive nature of Raman spectroscopy allows real-time monitoring of structural stability during
583 catalytic or electrochemical processes. Consequently, Raman analysis serves as an essential

584 complement to XANES and EXAFS, providing indirect yet critical evidence of local structural
585 modifications induced by single-atom incorporation in MXenes. During the formation of
586 CrN₄/MXene, structural and bonding changes induced by nitrogen doping were evident. Compared
587 with CrO₄/MXene, the CrN₄/MXene electrode exhibits a blue shift in characteristic Raman peaks,
588 indicating that nitrogen coordination causes lattice distortion and alters the grain size of the
589 material [97].

590

591 **5. Role of electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy in organic molecule** 592 **detoxification reactions**

593 EPR is a critical analytical technique for characterizing SAs@MXenes catalysts because it
594 provides direct, site-specific evidence of their active electronic structure and reaction pathways.

595 EPR detects the unpaired electrons associated with isolated metal centers, confirming that the
596 active sites remain atomically dispersed rather than aggregating into metallic clusters. Subtle
597 variations in g-values and hyperfine splitting patterns allow accurate determination of oxidation
598 states and the local coordination environments formed by MXene surface terminations, features
599 that conventional techniques such as TEM or XPS can only infer indirectly. In operando
600 conditions, EPR can detect short-lived radical intermediates (e.g., ·OH, O₂^{·-}) and transient metal-
601 oxo species, providing valuable insights into the activation pathways of pollutants and oxidants.

602 Moreover, comparing spectra before and after multiple catalytic cycles reveals whether single
603 atoms remain dispersed or begin to aggregate, thereby serving as a direct measure of catalyst
604 stability. This ability to simultaneously probe electronic, structural, and mechanistic features
605 makes EPR an indispensable tool for validating both the design and performance of
606 SAs@MXenes.

607 In the study by M. Li et al., EPR (Fig. 12(a)) was employed to identify the ROS generated in
608 the $\text{Co}_{\text{SA}}\text{-N-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x/\text{PMS}$ (peroxymonosulfate) system, providing essential mechanistic insights.
609 Using spin-trap agents, the EPR spectra revealed characteristic hexagonal signals $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{O}_2^-$
610 adduct signals, demonstrating that superoxide radicals were the dominant reactive species. Only
611 weak signals corresponding to $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{OH}$, $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{SO}_4^-$, and $\text{TEMP}\cdot^1\text{O}_2$ were observed. This
612 selective generation of $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ highlights its central role in the catalytic process. Electron-rich phenolic
613 pollutants transfer electrons to the $\text{Co-N}_2\text{O}_3$ active sites, which then reduce dissolved oxygen to
614 form $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$. Unlike the stronger oxidants $\cdot\text{OH}$ and SO_4^- which typically drive complete
615 mineralization, $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ has milder oxidizing power, promoting radical-radical coupling of phenolic
616 intermediates. Consequently, EPR provided direct experimental evidence that, rather than
617 indiscriminate deep oxidation, pollutant removal proceeds via a controlled self-coupling pathway
618 mediated by superoxide. This mechanistic insight highlights the unique chemistry of the $\text{Co-N}_2\text{O}_3$
619 coordination environment, which enables efficient PMS activation while selectively directing the
620 polymerization of organic contaminants [98].

621 EPR analysis also provided decisive evidence for the ROS generated by the Cu-single-atom
622 (Cu_{SA}) MXene catalyst during electro-PMS activation. Using a Bruker EMXnano spectrometer
623 with 5,5-dimethyl-1-piperidine N-oxide (DMPO) and 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine (TEMP) as spin
624 traps, the $\text{Cu}_{\text{SA}}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ system produced only a weak $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{OH}$ quartet (1:2:2:1, $a_{\text{N}} = a_{\text{H}} \approx$
625 14.9 G, $g \approx 2.0055$). In contrast, the Cu nanocluster and nanoparticle catalysts exhibited three- to
626 four-fold stronger $\cdot\text{OH}$ signals. Notably, the $\text{Cu}_{\text{SA}}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ catalyst exhibited a dominant
627 $\text{TEMP}\cdot^1\text{O}_2$ triplet (1:1:1, $a_{\text{N}} \approx 16.9$ G, $g \approx 2.0054$) that was nearly four- to five-fold more intense
628 than those of the nanocluster or nanoparticle analogues. Quantitative EPR analysis revealed ~ 302
629 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of singlet oxygen, which is approximately 93% of total ROS, while hydroxyl radicals

630 accounted for only $\sim 6 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$. These results demonstrate that atomically dispersed Cu-O₃ centers
631 activate PMS primarily through a non-radical electron-transfer pathway, wherein electrons from
632 the catalyst generate superoxide radicals, which subsequently recombine or are oxidized by Cu²⁺
633 to form singlet oxygen. This mechanistic evidence explains the superior and ultrafast degradation
634 of sulfamethoxazole achieved by the Cu_{SA}/Ti₃C₂T_x membrane, highlighting the unique reactivity
635 of isolated copper sites, which preferentially facilitate ¹O₂ generation over hydroxyl- or sulfate-
636 radical oxidation [99].

637 In another study, EPR confirmed that the Cr-N₄/MXene fluidic electrode selectively generates
638 singlet oxygen (¹O₂) rather than hydroxyl radicals during electrocatalytic O₂ activation. The time-
639 resolved spectra (Fig. 12(b)) displayed a strong three-line ¹O₂ TEMP adduct signal ($g \approx 2.005$)
640 with only trace DMPO- $\cdot\text{OH}$ features, whereas the nitrogen-free Cr-O₄ counterpart produced
641 intense $\cdot\text{OH}$ signals. Additional spectra (Fig. 12(f)) captured the DMPO-O₂ \cdot^- adduct ($\alpha_{\text{N}} \approx 12.9$
642 G, $\alpha_{\text{H}} \approx 10.3$ G, $g \approx 2.0057$), providing direct evidence for superoxide and hydroperoxyl
643 intermediates. Scavenger experiments (Fig. 12(g)) showed that the addition of superoxide
644 dismutase and furfuryl alcohol significantly reduced both the ¹O₂ signal and sulfamethoxazole
645 degradation efficiency, confirming $\cdot\text{OOH}/\text{O}_2\cdot^-$ as the key precursor. Collectively, the EPR results
646 indicate that N-doped Cr single-atom sites modify the electronic environment to promote highly
647 selective ¹O₂ generation, enabling efficient oxidation of electron-rich organic pollutants [97].

648 In a separate investigation, EPR analysis demonstrated that the Fe-N-C single-atom catalyst
649 activates PMS primarily through a high-valent Fe(IV)-oxo intermediate rather than free radicals.
650 In (Fig. 12(c)), DMPO spin-trapping spectra showed almost no characteristic quartet for hydroxyl
651 or sulfate radicals, while Fig. 10d exhibited a distinct signal corresponding to the DMPOX adduct,
652 formed during direct electron transfer from the catalyst surface to PMS. Furthermore, (Fig. 12(e))

653 displayed a persistent signal even after the addition of methanol or tert-butanol, confirming that
654 neither $\cdot\text{OH}$ nor $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ radicals dominate the oxidation process. Quenching with sodium azide and
655 1,4-benzoquinone partially suppressed the catalytic activity, consistent with a minor contribution
656 from singlet oxygen and superoxide intermediates. These EPR observations, supported by in situ
657 Mössbauer spectroscopy and X-ray absorption evidence of an Fe(IV)=O species, indicate that
658 atomically dispersed Fe-N_4 sites enable PMS to form a surface-bound Fe(IV)-oxo complex that
659 accepts electrons directly from organic pollutants. This nonradical oxidation pathway accounts for
660 the high selectivity and stability of the catalyst, as the Fe(IV) center facilitates the two-electron
661 oxidation of refractory organics while avoiding the non-selective reactivity typical of free radical
662 mechanism [100]. In another study, X. Guo et al. demonstrated that the degradation of bisphenol
663 A (BPA) by the $\text{Co}_{\text{SA}}\text{-NC}/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{MX}$ catalyst proceeds through a non-radical electron-transfer
664 pathway rather than via conventional ROS-mediated oxidation. Quenching experiments first
665 excluded the involvement of sulfate radicals, hydroxyl radicals, superoxide, and singlet oxygen,
666 as methanol, tert-butanol, and benzoic acid had negligible effects, nitro-blue tetrazolium showed
667 minimal reduction, and L-histidine failed to suppress BPA removal. The EPR spectra (Fig. 12(h))
668 showed no $\text{TEMP-}^1\text{O}_2$ triplet, confirming that singlet oxygen was not produced. When DMPO
669 was used as the trapping agent, distinct DMPOX adduct peaks appeared and persisted even after
670 the addition of methanol, furfuryl alcohol, or dimethyl sulfoxide, demonstrating that PMS
671 activation at the cobalt sites forms an electron-transfer complex rather than free radicals. This
672 DMPOX signature, supported by in situ Raman detection of a transient $\text{Co}_{\text{SA}}\text{-NC}/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{MX}\text{-PMS}^*$
673 band at 834 cm^{-1} and open-circuit potential shifts upon BPA addition, reveals that cobalt single-
674 atom/nanocluster ensembles create high-potential surface complexes capable of direct electron
675 transfer from BPA to PMS. Thus, the EPR results confirm a purely nonradical mechanism in which

676 asymmetrically coordinated CoN_1O_2 single atoms, assisted by neighboring Co nanoclusters,
677 stabilize PMS, accelerate interfacial charge transfer, and drive BPA polymerization without
678 generating conventional ROS [101].

679 Overall, EPR spectroscopy is a powerful and indispensable tool for elucidating the active sites
680 and reaction mechanisms of MXene-based single-atom catalysts (SACs) during the detoxification
681 of organic pollutants. It provides direct experimental evidence of reactive oxygen species (ROS)
682 generation and distinguishes between radical pathways ($\cdot\text{OH}$, $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$, $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$) and non-radical or
683 electron-transfer mechanisms ($^1\text{O}_2$, Fe(IV)=O , surface-bound charge transfer) with atomic-level
684 precision. By capturing transient intermediates and monitoring electronic structure variations, EPR
685 enables a clear correlation between metal coordination environments and catalytic performance.
686 Its unique ability to identify mechanistic transitions from aggressive radical oxidation to selective
687 non-radical or electron-transfer pathways highlights the role of atomically dispersed active centers
688 in achieving both high reactivity and long-term stability. Consequently, EPR validates the atomic
689 dispersion and structural durability of SAs@MXene catalysts and provides fundamental
690 mechanistic insights crucial for the rational design of next-generation catalytic systems aimed at
691 sustainable and selective environmental remediation. In addition to the advantages of the
692 characterization techniques, we have highlighted their limitations, as shown in Table 4.

693

694 **6. SAs@MXenes catalysts for organic pollutant detoxification**

695 SAs@MXenes has emerged as a highly efficient and tunable material for degrading and removing
696 organic pollutants from wastewater. The integration of atomically dispersed metal atoms onto
697 conductive MXene substrates combines the superior catalytic activity of single atoms with the
698 unique physicochemical properties of MXenes, including large surface area, high electrical

699 conductivity, and abundant surface functional groups. These features promote rapid electron
700 transfer, efficient activation of oxidants such as peroxymonosulfate (PMS), peroxydisulfate (PDS),
701 and H₂O₂, and enhanced generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which are essential for
702 decomposing persistent organic contaminants. Strong metal-support interaction between the single
703 atoms and MXene surface prevents atom aggregation and tunes the electronic structure, thereby
704 improving catalytic selectivity and stability during repeated degradation cycles. Furthermore, the
705 versatility in tailoring both MXene composition and single-atom type allows precise control over
706 catalytic pathways, enabling the efficient degradation of antibiotics, phenolic compounds, and
707 other recalcitrant pollutants under mild conditions. Owing to these advantages, SAs@MXenes
708 represents a promising class of next-generation catalysts for sustainable and high-performance
709 water purification technologies.

710

711 *6.1. SAs@MXenes membranes for wastewater treatment*

712 Two-dimensional catalytic ultrafiltration membranes were fabricated by assembling Ti₃C₂T_x
713 MXene nanosheets with atomically dispersed cobalt (Co) SAs via a solvothermal route followed
714 by low-temperature reduction. As shown in (Fig. 13(a)), the resulting N-coordinated Co-MXene
715 membrane exhibited a characteristic lamellar structure typical of two-dimensional membranes, as
716 confirmed by SEM and TEM analyses. In the absence of PMS, the degradation of carbamazepine
717 (CBZ) by all catalytic membranes was negligible (Fig. 13(b)) owing to the neutral charge of CBZ
718 and limited electrostatic interactions. Zeta-potential measurements (Fig. 13(c)) revealed that the
719 membrane loaded with 20 mg of catalyst possessed the most negative surface charge, enhancing
720 its catalytic affinity. As shown in (Fig. 13(d)), the optimized Co-MXene membrane achieved 100%
721 high CBZ degradation efficiency at pH 5 within 30 min, and maintained a high water permeability

722 of $\sim 900 \text{ L}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{bar}^{-1}$, breaking the traditional selectivity and permeability trade-off. This
723 remarkable performance is attributed to coordinatively unsaturated Co-N₁O₂ active sites that
724 accelerate electron transfer and enhance the generation of ROS, particularly singlet oxygen (¹O₂)
725 and high-valent Co=O species. Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy confirmed
726 the presence of both radical (SO₄^{•-}, •OH) and non-radical species, such as singlet oxygen (¹O₂),
727 while scavenger experiments verified that ¹O₂ was the dominant ROS. Additionally, high-valent
728 Co-O species participated in oxidative degradation via oxygen-atom transfer (OAT) pathways, as
729 evidenced by the transformation of methyl phenyl sulfoxide. A schematic illustration in (Fig. 13(e))
730 depicts the CBZ adsorption and degradation mechanism on the Co-MXene membrane surface.
731 Nano-confinement channels formed by closely stacked MXene lamellae enhanced water transport,
732 while atomically dispersed Co centers maintained high ROS turnover. The Co-MXene/PMS
733 system exhibited strong stability in natural water, achieving a cumulative throughput of 3000 L·m⁻²
734 and a 96% reduction in biofouling against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Furthermore, the membrane
735 maintained full CBZ degradation in the presence of anions, natural organic matter (NOM), and
736 microbial contaminants, confirming its robustness for real-water applications [102].

737 In a complementary system, an electroactive MXene filter (Fe_{SA}/Mo₂TiC₂T_x) was developed
738 by embedding atomically dispersed Fe SAs in Mo-vacancy-rich Ti-based MXene substrates. These
739 Mo vacancies serve dual functions: they anchor Fe atoms through strong Fe-O₆ octahedral
740 coordination and facilitate Fenton-like oxidation. The Mo₂TiC₂T_x MXene was synthesized by
741 selectively etching Al from Mo₂TiC₂ using HF (Fig. 14(a)). HAADF-STEM imaging (Fig. 14(b))
742 revealed bright atomic-scale features consistent with Fe SAs, and HRTEM images (Fig. 14(d))
743 confirmed their dispersion, as illustrated schematically in Fig. 14(c). Under an applied potential of
744 2.0 V, the Fe-MXene filter achieved 100% sulfamethoxazole (SMX) degradation within 2 seconds,

745 with a rate constant (k) of 2.89 min^{-1} (Fig. 14(e, f)). The degradation rate decreased in the presence
746 of methanol and tert-butyl alcohol (TBA), indicating radical involvement. Only the
747 $\text{Fe}_{\text{SA}}/\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x/\text{PMS}$ system exhibited a $\text{DMPO-SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ signal (Fig. 14(g)), confirming sulfate
748 radical formation. As the potential increased from 0 to 2.0 V, the concentrations of $\cdot\text{OH}$, $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$, and
749 $^1\text{O}_2$ all increased, with $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ showing the most significant increase from $63.1 \mu\text{mol/L}$ (67.1%) to
750 $108.1 \mu\text{mol/L}$ (80.7%) (Fig. 14(h)), establishing it as the dominant oxidant. DFT calculations were
751 employed to elucidate the electro-PMS activation. The charge distribution around the Fe_{SA} sites
752 (Fig. 14(j)) showed negatively charged oxygen atoms surrounding positively charged Fe centers,
753 producing a more uniform electron distribution than in the Fe-NP counterparts (Fig. 14(i)).
754 Electron-density maps (Fig. 14(k)) indicated that the Fe_{SA} sites act as electron donors to PMS,
755 consistent with the decrease in current observed in linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) upon PMS
756 addition, whereas the Fe-NP sites accept electrons, showing a slight increase in current (Fig. 14(l)).
757 The proposed electro-PMS activation mechanism is illustrated in Fig. 14(m). The system
758 demonstrated broad pH tolerance, high reusability, and excellent performance in real water,
759 confirming its suitability for continuous-flow purification [103].

760 A universal Lewis-acid molten-salt etching strategy was subsequently adopted to synthesize
761 MXene-supported SACs by reacting Ti_3AlC_2 MAX phases with CuCl_2 under Lewis-acid molten-
762 salt conditions (Fig. 15(a)). After soaking in HCl for six hours with ultrasonic assistance, spherical
763 Cu nanoparticles were completely removed, resulting in wrinkled surfaces and porous structures,
764 as observed in (Fig. 15(b,c)). TEM images (Fig. 15(d, e)) confirmed the absence of Cu particles
765 and revealed highly dispersed Cu atoms on the two-dimensional layered $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$. The bright dots
766 within the yellow circle in Fig. 15(f) correspond to isolated Cu single atoms. Fig. 15(g) shows the
767 formation of Ti vacancies with strong reducing capabilities, which effectively stabilized atomically

768 dispersed Cu atoms coordinated in a Cu-O₃ environment on the MXene surface. EDX images are
769 presented in (Fig. 15(h, i)). The catalyst's oxidation performance was evaluated using BPA as a
770 model pollutant. As shown in (Fig. 15(j)), PMS alone removed only 5.70% of BPA within 20
771 minutes, indicating limited oxidative capacity. However, the Cu_{SA}/MXene-900 catalyst exhibited
772 nearly complete selectivity for generating singlet oxygen (¹O₂) during PMS activation. To assess
773 its practical applicability, the catalyst was uniformly dispersed and vacuum-filtered onto a
774 polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) membrane to fabricate a continuous-flow wastewater treatment
775 system (Fig. 15(k-m)). The resulting membrane exhibited excellent flexibility and well-preserved
776 surface morphology, as shown in (Fig. 15(n, o)). This high ¹O₂ yield enabled efficient BPA
777 degradation, achieving complete removal within 10 minutes, with a pseudo-first-order rate
778 constant of 0.6117 min⁻¹ and a high turnover frequency (TOF) of 4.71 × 10² min⁻¹. The catalyst also
779 achieved a mineralization efficiency of 75.96%, broad pH tolerance, and resistance to inorganic
780 ions and radical scavengers. Minimal Cu leaching and >90% retention of catalytic activity after
781 five cycles confirmed its outstanding stability. EPR and scavenger tests identified ¹O₂ as the
782 dominant ROS, with weakly charged Cu sites on MXene facilitating PMS adsorption and
783 promoting the formation of SO₅^{•-} intermediates that drive selective ¹O₂ generation. Notably, the
784 Cu_{SA}/MXene-900 membrane maintained excellent degradation performance even in real
785 wastewater with high salinity, achieving effective removal of chemical oxygen demand (COD) and
786 total organic carbon (TOC). These findings underscore its strong potential as a scalable solution
787 for industrial wastewater treatment. A schematic of the Cu_{SA}/MXene-triggered PMS activation is
788 presented in (Fig. 15(p)) [104].

789 These studies highlight the significant potential of MXene-supported single-atom catalysts for
790 the selective and robust activation of PMS through well-defined coordination environments, such

791 as Co-N₁O₂, Fe-O₆, and Cu-O₃. The atomic dispersion of metal sites enhances catalytic activity
792 and selectivity by facilitating the controlled generation of ROS (e.g., ¹O₂, Co=O, SO₄^{•-}) and
793 improves membrane durability, water permeability, and resistance to biofouling. These insights
794 provide a foundation for the rational design of SAC-integrated MXene membranes, supporting
795 their use in high-performance, scalable water purification systems under realistic conditions.

796 C. Meng et al. reported that the degradation of organic micropollutants (OMPs) in the Co-N-
797 Ti_{3-x}C₂T_y membrane system occurs through a highly efficient nano-confined catalytic oxidation
798 mechanism, in which atomically dispersed cobalt sites activate PMS to generate reactive oxygen
799 species (ROS). Single Co atoms anchored at asymmetric Co-N₁C₂ sites within the MXene lattice
800 serve as active centers, promoting rapid electron transfer that cleaves the O-O bond of PMS to
801 produce sulfate radicals (SO₄^{•-}), hydroxyl radicals (•OH), and singlet oxygen (¹O₂). Within the
802 confined 0.57 nm interlayer channels of the MXene membrane, PMS and pollutants are brought
803 into close contact, while the nanoconfinement effect and asymmetric coordination environment
804 significantly lower the energy barrier for ROS generation, enabling PMS decomposition within
805 femtoseconds. These generated ROS species act synergistically to oxidize organic pollutants such
806 as ranitidine, tetracycline, and phenol through hydroxylation, dealkylation, and ring cleavage,
807 ultimately leading to complete mineralization into CO₂ and H₂O. Meanwhile, the conductive Ti₃-
808 xC₂T_y framework facilitates efficient electron transport, enhancing the redox cycling of Co species
809 and ensuring stable catalytic activity. This integration of single-atom catalysis and
810 nanoconfinement not only enhances the degradation kinetics by 10⁵-10⁷ times compared with non-
811 confined systems but also ensures the ultrafast, selective, and environmentally safe elimination of
812 OMPs without producing toxic byproducts. The Co-N-Ti_{3-x}C₂T_y membrane exhibited outstanding
813 performance in the degradation of various OMPs under continuous flow conditions. When

814 combined with PMS, the membrane achieved 100% removal efficiency for pollutants such as
815 ranitidine, tetracycline (TC), and ofloxacin (OFX), along with more than 90% degradation of
816 bisphenol A (BPA), phenol, and carbamazepine (CBZ), even at an ultrahigh water flux of
817 approximately 2157 LMH and a short retention time of 13.2 milliseconds. Total organic carbon
818 (TOC) removal reached nearly 99%, confirming that most pollutants were completely mineralized
819 into CO₂ and H₂O. Importantly, the system maintained 100% removal efficiency and structural
820 integrity during 130 hours of continuous operation, with cobalt leaching below 3%. In addition,
821 the membrane demonstrated excellent stability and reusability across different water matrices,
822 including tap water and river water, maintaining over 95% degradation efficiency in the presence
823 of natural organic matter and inorganic ions [105].

824

825 *6.2. SAs@MXenes for non-radical pathways and selective organic pollutant removal*

826 A coupled synthetic strategy involving sequential etching, exfoliation, and reduction was used to
827 introduce a high density of titanium (Ti) vacancies into Ti₃C₂T_x MXenes, enabling the stable
828 anchoring of atomically dispersed cobalt single atoms (Co-SAs). Using a defect-trapping method
829 combined with NaBH₄ reduction, stable Co single atoms were effectively immobilized on two-
830 dimensional Ti₃C₂T_x nanosheets for efficient activation of PMS and Ranitidine (RAN)
831 degradation, as illustrated in (Fig. 16(a)). The engineered Co_{SA}/MXene catalyst exhibited
832 outstanding catalytic activity, achieving complete (100%) degradation of RAN with reaction
833 kinetics 1.11-6643.53 times faster than previously reported systems. As shown in (Fig. 16(d)),
834 PMS alone achieved only 23.4% RAN removal, indicating that the intrinsic oxidation capacity was
835 limited. Upon the addition of the catalyst, the observed rate constant (K_{obs}) increased from 0.066
836 min⁻¹ to 0.167 min⁻¹ (Fig. 16(e)). Increasing the PMS concentration from 45 mg/L to 50 mg/L

837 further elevated the apparent rate constant from 0.120 min^{-1} to 0.167 min^{-1} within 20 minutes (Fig.
838 16(f)). The degradation efficiency strongly depended on the solution's initial pH. As shown in (Fig.
839 16(g)), the RAN removal efficiencies were 44.75%, 82.42%, 100.00%, 92.01%, and 18.87% at pH
840 3.0, 5.0, 7.0, 9.0, and 11.0, respectively. Zeta potential analysis (Fig. 16(h)) revealed a shift in
841 surface charge from $+24.6 \text{ mV}$ to -32.1 mV , indicating that Co^{2+} leaching was primarily influenced
842 by the H^+ concentration. The engineered Ti vacancies served as electron-deficient anchoring sites,
843 stabilizing the positively charged Co species through Co-O_6 coordination. These features promote
844 efficient $\text{Co}^{2+}/\text{Co}^{3+}$ redox cycling while suppressing Co^{2+} leaching by electrostatically confining
845 the metal centers within the MXene interlayers, resulting in exceptional structural stability and
846 long-term durability.

847 DFT calculation were performed using the Vienna Ab initio Simulation Package (VASP) with
848 the GGA-PBE functional and DFT-D3 dispersion corrections to investigate PMS activation on
849 pristine MXene, nitrogen-doped MXene (N-MXene), and cobalt-doped MXene (Co-MXene).
850 Among these, Co-MXene showed the most favorable behavior, exhibiting moderate PMS
851 adsorption energy (-2.76 eV), the highest electron transfer to PMS (0.93 e^-), and the longest O-O
852 bond length (1.489 \AA), all of which indicate enhanced O-O bond cleavage and efficient PMS
853 activation (Fig. 16(b)). Charge-density-difference plots revealed significant electron donation from
854 the $\text{Co-N}_1\text{O}_2$ coordination site to PMS, facilitating the formation of singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$) and high-
855 valent Co=O species rather than conventional $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ or $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals (Fig. 16(c)). These results
856 provide direct evidence of a non-radical degradation mechanism during the oxidation of ranitidine
857 [106]. Furthermore, a coordination-modulation strategy was applied to develop fluidic single-atom
858 electrodes capable of selectively generating $^1\text{O}_2$ from molecular oxygen. This was achieved by
859 converting Cr-O_4 coordination environments into Cr-N_4 sites on nitrogen-doped MXene supports,

860 thereby tuning the electronic structure and promoting end-on O₂ adsorption. This adsorption
861 configuration stabilized the OOH intermediate, which is a key precursor for the formation of ¹O₂.
862 Structural characterization through XRD, XPS, FTIR, and EXAFS confirmed the successful
863 synthesis of atomically dispersed Cr-N₄ coordination sites. When tested in a flow-through
864 electrochemical reactor, the Cr-N₄/MXene electrode achieved ~100% sulfamethoxazole (SMX)
865 degradation within 40 minutes, with a rate constant of 0.097 min⁻¹, which was approximately 2.5
866 times higher than that of the Cr-O₄/MXene system. It also achieved 94.7% BPA removal (rate
867 constant: 0.089 min⁻¹) and maintained a TOC removal efficiency of 56.4% after six reuse cycles
868 [97].

869 In another study, a dual-carrier Co single-atom catalyst (Co_{SA}/MCSM_x) was synthesized using
870 mesoporous carbon/MXene nanosheets (Fig. 17(a)). As shown in (Fig. 17(b)), the combination of
871 Co_{SA}/MCSM_x and PMS enabled nearly 100% BPA removal. The pseudo-first-order rate constant
872 (k) for BPA degradation in the Co_{SA}/MCSM_x+PMS system was 0.536 min⁻¹, which was 1.3, 5.5,
873 7.5, and 25.5 times higher than those observed for CoNP/CSM_x+PMS, CoNP/MC+PMS,
874 MCSM_x+PMS, and CoNP/M_x+PMS systems, respectively (Fig. 17(c)). The degradation was
875 minimally affected by the presence of 500 mM TBA (Fig. 17(d)), indicating that the dominant
876 mechanism was a non-radical electron transfer process (ETP). The Co-N₄ coordination
877 environment, along with neighboring graphitic N sites, facilitated PMS activation through ETP,
878 achieving nearly complete degradation with 72% TOC removal. A graphitized oxidation structure
879 (GOS) was proposed to facilitate this interaction.

880 Mechanistic analysis revealed two principal pathways for the degradation of BPA. Pathway I
881 involves the β-scission of phenolic intermediates, producing oxygenated fragments (TP3-TP6),
882 while Pathway II proceeds through C-C or C-O coupling of phenoxy radicals, leading to the

883 formation of polycyclic products (TP7-TP9) (Fig. 17(e,f)). ETP-induced polymerization reactions
884 resulted in the formation of insoluble polymer networks on the catalyst surface. This was
885 confirmed by XPS and TGA analyses, which showed increased carbon deposition after the
886 reaction. Repeated use of the catalyst led to partial deactivation due to polymer accumulation;
887 however, calcination effectively restored its activity. The system displayed high selectivity toward
888 electron-rich aromatic pollutants such as BPA, phenol, and 4-chlorophenol, while exhibiting
889 limited activity toward electron-deficient compounds such as 4-nitrophenol and benzoic acid,
890 further supporting the specificity of the ETP mechanism [107].

891 In another study, a nitrogen-modification strategy was employed to construct a Co-N₂O₃
892 coordination environment on Ti₃C₂T_x MXene [98]. This configuration created asymmetrical
893 electronic microregions around atomically dispersed Co sites, enabling selective PMS activation
894 to generate singlet oxygen (¹O₂) as the dominant ROS. This Co_{SA}-N-Ti₃C₂T_x system followed a
895 radical oxidation pathway, in which the moderate oxidative potential and selectivity of ¹O₂ favored
896 pollutant self-coupling rather than deep mineralization. This mechanism enabled the complete
897 degradation of electron-rich phenolic compounds, such as acetaminophen and 4-chlorophenol,
898 within 3 minutes. To evaluate the effects of the substrate, PMS activation by bare Ti₃C₂T_x and
899 annealed Ti₃C₂T_x was examined (Fig. 18(a)). The Co_{SA}-N-Ti₃C₂T_x catalyst significantly
900 outperformed both the homogeneous Co²⁺ and heterogeneous Co₃O₄ systems, exhibiting turnover
901 frequencies (TOFs) 39 and 816 times higher, respectively (Fig. 18(b)). Similar to Co₃O₄, the
902 catalyst was readily recovered using a PTFE membrane. Moreover, its performance exceeded that
903 of all Co-SACs reported in the past three years, as indicated by the composite kinetic constant per
904 active site (K_{emp}) values (Fig. 18(c)). Mechanistically, electron-rich pollutants donate electrons to
905 Co-N₂O₃ sites, thereby reducing dissolved oxygen (DO) to form ¹O₂. This electron-transfer-driven

906 redox mechanism governs the catalyst's selectivity. The system also exhibited strong resistance to
907 inorganic anions and maintained 100% removal efficiency in real wastewater under continuous-
908 flow conditions, even at a hydraulic retention time of 0.98 seconds, demonstrating its potential for
909 scalable and rapid water purification.

910 The underlying mechanism of PMS activation was further explored using VASP with the PBE
911 functional, PAW pseudopotentials, and DFT-D3 dispersion corrections. The optimized Co-N₂O₃
912 coordination structure exhibited high thermodynamic stability with a formation energy of -15.77
913 eV. Mulliken charge analysis indicated a reduced positive charge on the Co center (+0.20 (Fig.
914 18(d)), indicating enhanced electron donation from the surrounding nitrogen ligands. Two types
915 of oxygen ligands, hydroxyl oxygen (Type I) and terminal oxygen (Type III), exhibited elongated
916 O-O bond lengths and distinct adsorption energies, both contributing to effective PMS activation
917 (Fig. 18(e)). Based on these results, a mechanism for the selective generation of $\cdot\text{O}_2$ radicals in the
918 Co_{SA}-N-Ti₃C₂T_x/PMS system was proposed (Fig. 18(f)).

919 Adsorption studies indicated that PMS preferentially binds through its hydroxyl oxygen,
920 forming electron-deficient regions on the catalyst surface. Among the competing species,
921 acetaminophen (ACE) exhibited stronger adsorption and greater electron transfer than dissolved
922 oxygen (DO), facilitating PMS activation and promoting DO reduction to $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ radicals. Electron-
923 density difference plots and adsorption-energy analyses further confirmed this selective $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$
924 generation pathway. To simulate municipal wastewater treatment conditions, a colloidal Co_{SA}-N-
925 Ti₃C₂T_x solution was pumped through a PTFE membrane, forming the core of a simple, scalable
926 treatment system (Fig. 18(g)). The system demonstrated excellent wastewater treatment
927 performance, achieving high removal efficiency for ACE as a model pollutant (Fig. 18(h)) [98]. In
928 a related study, the spatial distribution of copper (Cu) active sites on Ti₃C₂T_x MXene was

929 systematically investigated to assess its influence on PMS activation and contaminant degradation.
930 Atomic layer deposition (ALD) was used to fabricate MXene catalysts with three distinct Cu
931 configurations: single atoms (SA-Cu), nanoclusters (C-Cu), and thin films (F-Cu). The SA-Cu-
932 MXene system achieved approximately 65.4% degradation of sulfamethoxazole (SMX) within 60
933 minutes, representing a 42.4% improvement over the undecorated MXene/PMS system. The C-
934 Cu-MXene/PMS system exhibited even greater activity, degrading more than 95.0% of SMX in
935 60 minutes while maintaining excellent stability over five cycles. The pseudo-first-order rate
936 constants (k), normalized by Cu content, were 0.143 min^{-1} (SA-Cu), 0.187 min^{-1} (C-Cu), and 0.006
937 min^{-1} (F-Cu), confirming the superior catalytic efficiency of the Cu nanoclusters. Among the three
938 configurations, C-Cu-MXene demonstrated the most efficient catalytic performance, attributed to
939 its highest PMS adsorption energy (-5.435 eV), enhanced generation of $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ radicals, and SMX
940 degradation efficiency of 97.3%, with a corresponding rate constant of 0.0485 min^{-1} . LC-MS
941 analysis revealed distinct degradation pathways for SMX, with C-Cu-MXene promoting the
942 formation of a wider variety of less toxic intermediates than the SA-Cu and F-Cu systems. The
943 initial cleavage of the S-N bond in SMX generated P1 and P2, with P2 subsequently transforming
944 into the less toxic product P4 in the C-Cu-MXene system. The degradation process was
945 predominantly driven by $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ -induced hydroxylation, particularly at the ortho position of the -
946 NH_2 group, leading to the opening of the isoxazole ring and the formation of polyhydroxylated
947 intermediates, such as P7, P9, P11, and P12. Additional transformations included the oxidative
948 cleavage of C-C and C-N bonds within the isoxazole and amine groups, forming intermediates P13
949 and P14 through a combined $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}/\cdot\text{OH}$ attack. Furthermore, amino-coupling reactions between
950 SMX molecules produced dimers (P16) and hydroxylated trimers (P17), demonstrating a complex
951 degradation network initiated by the C-Cu-MXene catalyst. The dual-radical environment in the

952 C-Cu-MXene system, featuring both $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ and $\cdot\text{OH}$ species, facilitated deep oxidative degradation
953 while minimizing the accumulation of polymerized or high-mass byproducts. Compared with the
954 other Cu configurations, C-Cu-MXene generated fewer high-mass and toxic intermediates,
955 confirming its ability to achieve more complete and environmentally benign pollutant degradation
956 [108].

957 The removal mechanism of BPA using the synthesized $\text{Co}_{\text{SA-NC}}/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{MX}$ catalyst was primarily
958 governed by a nonradical electron-transfer process (ETP) rather than conventional radical
959 oxidation. In this system, asymmetrically coordinated CoN_1O_2 single-atom sites and Co
960 nanoclusters (NCs) act synergistically to activate PMS and form metastable surface complexes
961 denoted as $\text{Co}_{\text{SA-NC}}/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{MX-PMS}^*$. These surface complexes served as efficient electron
962 mediators, enabling direct electron transfer from BPA molecules to PMS without generating
963 reactive radicals such as $\cdot\text{OH}$ or $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$. The graphitic carbon layers and the holey MXene substrate
964 formed a highly conductive network that accelerated interfacial charge transfer, while graphitic N-
965 C sites enhanced π - π interactions with the aromatic rings of BPA, promoting adsorption on the
966 catalyst surface. Upon PMS activation, electrons from BPA were rapidly transferred to the Co
967 active centers *via* the $\text{Co}_{\text{SA-NC}}/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{MX-PMS}^*$ complex, oxidizing BPA into phenoxy radicals that
968 subsequently underwent C-C and C-O coupling to form polymerized intermediates. These
969 polymeric products were immobilized on the catalyst surface, resulting in effective BPA removal
970 and a significant reduction of total organic carbon (TOC). Overall, the synergistic interaction
971 between single Co atoms and Co nanoclusters enabled ultrafast non-radical PMS activation and
972 polymerization-driven BPA degradation through an advanced Fenton-like mechanism [101].

973 The removal of Pb-EDTA using the MXene-supported Co_3Ti and single-atom Co catalyst
974 ($\text{Co}@\text{MXene}$) occurs through a synergistic PMS activation mechanism that enables efficient

975 decomplexation of Pb-EDTA and complete recovery of Pb^{2+} ions. A proposed electron transport
976 mechanism for the Co@MXene/PMS process is illustrated in (Fig. 19(a)). In this mechanism, the
977 Co_3Ti alloy and single-atom Co sites serve as dual active centers that activate PMS through distinct
978 electron-transfer pathways. The Co_3Ti sites facilitate the formation of high-valent Co(IV) species,
979 while the single-atom Co sites generate reactive oxygen species. These species effectively attack
980 and break the strong chelating bonds of Pb-EDTA, releasing free Pb^{2+} ions into the solution. The
981 released Pb^{2+} ions are subsequently adsorbed onto the MXene surface or precipitated as $\text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$
982 under alkaline conditions, achieving complete Pb recovery. The Co@MXene/PMS system
983 achieved 93.6% Pb-EDTA degradation within 30 minutes (Fig. 19(b)) and 100% total Pb removal
984 within 15 minutes (Fig. 19(c)). The catalyst exhibited excellent stability and reusability,
985 maintaining an efficiency of over 80% after four cycles. Furthermore, the system demonstrated
986 self-regeneration ability through oxygen-transfer reactions between O- Co_3Ti and Co_3Ti -O, as well
987 as through the intrinsic reducibility of the MXene support, which converts Co(III) back to Co(II).
988 This dual-regeneration mechanism sustains the activity of the low-valent cobalt species, thereby
989 preventing catalyst deactivation. Overall, the Co@MXene catalyst offers an efficient, pH-stable
990 (3-9), and recyclable platform for Pb-EDTA removal [109].

991 H. Song et al. reported the degradation of organic pollutants using MXene-supported single-
992 atom cobalt catalysts ($\text{Co}@\text{Ti}_{2-x}\text{N}$) that operate through a synergistic radical and nonradical
993 oxidation mechanism, primarily involving PMS activation. When PMS interacts with Co single
994 atoms anchored at Ti-vacancy sites in MXene ($\text{Co}@\text{Ti}_{2-x}\text{N}$), redox activation occurs, producing
995 reactive oxygen species such as hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$) and sulfate radicals ($\text{SO}_4\cdot^-$). These radicals
996 exhibit strong oxidative potential and rapidly mineralize refractory organic pollutants such as
997 carbamazepine (CBZ), sulfamethoxazole (SMX), and 2,4-dichlorophenol (2,4-DCP) within

998 seconds. In addition to these radical pathways, a nonradical electron-transfer process also occurs.
999 PMS adsorbs onto the MXene surface, and electrons are transferred directly between PMS and
1000 pollutant molecules without forming free radicals. This process enhances selectivity and
1001 minimizes the risk of undesired side reactions. A distinctive feature of the MXene-supported Co
1002 catalyst is its ability to undergo redox cycling. The Ti atoms in the MXene substrate, which are
1003 highly reducible, continuously regenerate active Co(II) sites by reducing Co(III) to Co(II). As
1004 shown in (Fig. 19(d)), when Ti₂N MXene is introduced into a conventional Co(II)/PMS system,
1005 the SMX degradation rate of SMX increases significantly, indicating that MXene enhances redox
1006 cycling between Co(II) and Co(III) by donating electrons from its Ti sites, thereby accelerating
1007 PMS activation. The characteristic absorption peak of Co(III) (around 540 nm) decreases in
1008 intensity in the presence of MXene, confirming the reduction of Co(III) to Co(II) and sustained
1009 catalytic activity (Fig. 19(e)). After four consecutive cycles, a slight decrease in performance was
1010 observed due to the oxidation of Ti atoms to TiO₂, which reduced MXene's electron-donating
1011 ability (Fig. 19(f)). Despite this, the catalyst maintained excellent degradation efficiency in actual
1012 river water, confirming its stability and practical applicability (Fig. 19(g)). The complete
1013 PMS/Co@Ti_{2-x}N degradation mechanism is illustrated in (Fig. 19(h)). Within the PMS/Co@Ti₂₋
1014 _xN composite, complete degradation of all pollutants occurred within two minutes, with 2,4-DCP
1015 achieving 99.1% removal in just 40 seconds, significantly outperforming PMS alone or adsorption-
1016 based processes. The catalyst remained highly active across a wide pH range and performed even
1017 better under alkaline conditions due to strong Co-anchoring at Ti vacancies and the excellent
1018 reducibility of the MXene support [110]. The degradation of BPA using interlayer nanoconfined
1019 Cu single-atom/MXene nanochannels (Cu_{SA}/MXene) was investigated by Z. Wang et al. The
1020 process proceeds through a synergistic mechanism involving efficient PMS activation and

1021 enhanced mass transport within confined nanochannels. The atomically dispersed Cu single atoms,
1022 stabilized in a Cu-O₃ coordination environment, dynamically cycle between Cu(I) and Cu(II)
1023 oxidation states to activate PMS and generate reactive oxygen species including singlet oxygen
1024 (¹O₂), hydroxyl radicals (•OH), sulfate radicals (SO₄•⁻), and superoxide radicals (O₂•⁻). Among
1025 these, ¹O₂ was identified as the dominant species responsible for selective oxidation. The interlayer
1026 confinement (1.37 nm spacing) enriched BPA and PMS near active sites, shortened diffusion paths,
1027 and reduced the PMS activation energy barrier to 0.074 eV, thereby accelerating the generation of
1028 ROS and pollutant degradation. Consequently, the Cu_{SA}/MXene catalyst achieved 94.9% BPA
1029 removal within 5 minutes and exhibited excellent stability with negligible Cu leaching (42.6 µg/L).
1030 Kinetic analysis showed that the confined catalyst exhibited the highest first-order rate constant of
1031 0.479 min⁻¹, maintaining over 80% of its original activity after five cycles. The system achieved
1032 96.5% TOC removal and over 90% UV₂₅₄ reduction in industrial wastewater within 2 hours,
1033 demonstrating effective elimination of aromatic and complex organic compounds. The broad-
1034 spectrum degradation performance included 96.5% removal of phenol, 91.6% of SMX, 85.0% of
1035 CEZ, 97.6% of rhodamine B, and 99.8% of acid orange 7, confirming its versatility and high
1036 reactivity. The degradation pathway involved the hydroxylation, ring opening, and oxidation of
1037 BPA into low-toxicity intermediates such as catechol, hydroxybenzoic acid, and oxalic acid,
1038 confirming its effective mineralization. Overall, the Cu_{SA}/MXene system combines atomic-level
1039 catalytic precision with nanoconfinement effects to achieve ultrafast, selective, and
1040 environmentally safe BPA degradation [100]. A summary of SAs@MXenes composites for
1041 treating organic pollutants is presented in Table 5.

1042

1043 *6.3. SAs@MXenes catalyst stability evolution through reusability tests*

1044 The $\text{Co}_{\text{SA}}\text{-N-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ catalyst demonstrated good stability via reusability experiments. Even after
1045 four consecutive cycles, the system still achieved complete pollutant removal within a short
1046 reaction time, although a slight decline in degradation rate was observed with successive runs, as
1047 shown in (Fig. 20(a)). This minor decrease indicates some gradual loss of activity, yet the catalyst
1048 maintained high removal efficiency [98]. Moreover, in the first four cycles, the catalyst maintains
1049 high activity, achieving about 81% Pb-EDTA removal, indicating good catalytic stability and
1050 sustained PMS activation. However, starting with the fifth cycle, removal efficiency declines
1051 significantly, and after 10 cycles (Fig. 20(b)), it drops to around 12% for Pb-EDTA. This gradual
1052 loss in performance suggests that the catalyst's active sites are progressively deactivated, possibly
1053 due to surface oxidation, structural changes, or loss of accessible cobalt active centers during
1054 repeated reactions [109]. Furthermore, the cycling performance of the $\text{Co@Ti}_{2-x}\text{N}$ catalyst for
1055 SMX degradation during repeated PMS activation experiments. In the initial cycles, the
1056 degradation curves are steep, indicating rapid pollutant removal and strong catalytic activity.
1057 However, after successive reuse cycles, the degradation rate gradually slows, and by the fourth
1058 cycle, the curve becomes noticeably flatter, indicating reduced catalytic efficiency. This decline
1059 occurs because the exposed Ti atoms in the MXene support are progressively oxidized during
1060 repeated reactions, which weakens the catalyst's ability to regenerate active cobalt species and
1061 accelerate PMS activation. As a result, the system loses the accelerated reaction behavior observed
1062 in earlier runs, leading to slower SMX degradation in later cycles [110]. (Fig.20(c)) demonstrates
1063 the operational stability and reusability of the $\text{CrN}_4/\text{MXene}$ fluidic catalyst during repeated
1064 electrocatalytic degradation cycles. The total organic carbon (TOC) removal efficiency remains
1065 nearly constant across six consecutive runs, with only a slight decline. This indicates that the
1066 catalyst maintains its structural integrity and catalytic activity without significant deactivation or

1067 loss of active sites. Therefore, the synthesized catalyst exhibits excellent durability and can sustain
1068 effective pollutant mineralization over multiple cycles [97]. Y. Peng et al.'s results show the
1069 recycling performance of the MX/Cu-G-CN over seven successive degradation cycles (Fig. 20(d)).
1070 The ciprofloxacin removal efficiency remains above 80% even after repeated use, with only a
1071 slight decline observed. This demonstrates that the catalyst preserves its structural integrity and
1072 active sites without significant deactivation or metal leaching. Therefore, the MX/Cu-G-CN
1073 catalyst exhibits excellent stability and reusability [111]. A summary of SAs@MXenes and other
1074 SAC supports, and conventional composites for treating organic pollutants, along with a
1075 comparative assessment of catalytic performance, is presented in Table 6. Furthermore, in water-
1076 and oxygen-rich environments, MXene surfaces are prone to gradual oxidation, often leading to
1077 the formation of TiO₂ or other oxides that alter the material's surface chemistry and structural
1078 integrity. Such surface degradation directly affects the anchoring stability of single metal atoms,
1079 as oxidation can modify or eliminate functional groups that serve as coordination sites, resulting
1080 in atom migration, aggregation into nanoparticles, or eventual detachment. To enhance long-term
1081 stability, several strategies have been proposed, including surface passivation through protective
1082 coatings or controlled functionalization, compositing MXenes with stable matrices such as
1083 polymers, carbon materials, or metal oxides, and constructing hybrid structures that shield the
1084 MXene surface from oxidation while maintaining accessibility to active sites [127, 128].

1085

1086 *6.4. SAs@MXenes performance evaluation in real water matrix*

1087 The Co_{SA}-N-Ti₃C₂T_x catalyst performance was further validated through real water samples,
1088 including tap water, river water, and municipal wastewater. In all these complex water matrices,
1089 efficient acetaminophen removal was achieved within 3 minutes, with removal efficiencies ranging

1090 from approximately 79% to 89% (Fig. 20(e)). Despite the presence of natural ions and organic
1091 matter that typically hinder oxidation processes, the catalyst maintained strong degradation
1092 capability, demonstrating good resistance to environmental interference and confirming its
1093 applicability for real-world water purification [98]. Moreover, the practical applicability of the Co-
1094 SA/MXene catalyst for RAN removal in different real water matrices, including ultrapure water,
1095 tap water, river water, secondary effluent, and lake water (Fig. 20(f)). The results show that RAN
1096 degradation remains nearly complete in ultrapure, tap, and river water, indicating that common
1097 background ions and natural constituents have minimal interference with PMS activation by Co-
1098 SA/MXene. Although removal efficiency decreases slightly in more complex matrices, such as
1099 secondary effluent and lake water, due to high levels of organic matter and competing species,
1100 complete degradation of RAN is still achieved within 60 minutes [106]. Furthermore, (Fig. 20(g))
1101 evaluates the CrN₄/MXene catalyst performance in complex real water matrices, including river
1102 water and pharmaceutical wastewater spiked with pollutants. The results show that the degradation
1103 efficiency remains as high as 95%, even in the presence of competing ions and natural organic
1104 matter. This confirms that the CrN₄/MXene catalyst generates selective singlet oxygen effectively
1105 and is resistant to interference from background constituents [97]. Moreover, (Fig. 20(h, i))
1106 illustrates the common inorganic anions influence ciprofloxacin degradation by the MX/Cu-G-CN
1107 catalyst under visible-light/PMS activation. The results show that although anions such as Cl⁻,
1108 SO₄²⁻, H₂PO₄⁻, HCO₃⁻, and CO₃²⁻ slow the degradation rate to varying extents, MX/Cu-G-CN still
1109 maintains high removal efficiency under most conditions, demonstrating strong resistance to anion
1110 interference. Among the tested species, bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) and carbonate (CO₃²⁻) exert the
1111 strongest inhibitory effect, reducing removal efficiency to around 50% because they consume
1112 reactive radicals and convert them into less-oxidative carbonate radicals. In contrast, sulfate and

1113 phosphate ions cause only slight reductions in performance. The degradation performance of
1114 ciprofloxacin in different real water bodies, including tap water, artificial lake water, and river
1115 water. Despite the presence of natural organic matter and dissolved ions in these complex matrices,
1116 the MX/Cu-G-CN/PMS/visible-light system still achieves more than 80% CIP removal,
1117 demonstrating strong adaptability under complex environmental conditions. The small
1118 performance differences among water sources arise from differences in water quality and
1119 competing species, yet the catalyst consistently maintains high degradation efficiency [111].

1120

1121 *6.5. In situ spectroscopic mechanism studies*

1122 To monitor reaction intermediates in real time and elucidate catalytic pathways, in situ/operando
1123 spectroscopic techniques are highly desirable. A greater emphasis on advanced techniques such as
1124 XAS (XANES/EXAFS) and diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFT)
1125 is essential [129, 130]. These techniques are widely used in electrochemical and photochemical
1126 energy-conversion studies to identify active sites, monitor dynamic structural evolution, and define
1127 reaction pathways under working conditions. Such mechanisms are crucial for correlating
1128 experimental observations with DFT calculations and for reliable reaction models. In this review,
1129 we have discussed in situ Raman spectroscopy for investigating SAs@MXenes during the catalytic
1130 detoxification of organic pollutants. In situ Raman spectroscopy is a powerful technique for
1131 monitoring chemical and structural changes directly on a catalyst surface during the reaction,
1132 without interrupting the reaction environment. A laser beam is focused on the catalyst, and the
1133 scattered light is analyzed to obtain vibrational information about chemical bonds and surface
1134 species. Because measurements are conducted under real reaction conditions, this method enables

1135 real-time observation of intermediate formation, bond interactions, and reaction pathways
1136 [129,130].

1137 L. Jin et al. reported the time-dependent in situ Raman spectra of the CrN₄/MXene and
1138 CrO₄/MXene electrodes during electrocatalytic operation, which help explain the superior SMX
1139 removal performance of the CrN₄/MXene system. As the reaction proceeds, a new Raman peak
1140 appears at around 870 cm⁻¹ on the CrN₄/MXene electrode, corresponding to the O-O stretching
1141 vibration of superoxide species (Cr-O₂^{•-}) formed via end-on adsorption of oxygen on the single-
1142 atom Cr active sites. This intermediate is crucial because it subsequently transforms into ·OOH
1143 and finally generates singlet oxygen (¹O₂), which selectively oxidizes electron-rich pollutants such
1144 as SMX. In contrast, the CrO₄/MXene electrode shows only slight spectral shifts without the
1145 formation of new intermediate peaks, indicating inefficient oxygen activation. Thus, CrN₄/MXene
1146 effectively generates reactive oxygen intermediates required for continuous ¹O₂ production, which
1147 directly leads to the faster SMX degradation observed in the catalytic experiments [97].

1148 Furthermore, the in-situ Raman spectra (Fig. 21(a,b)) showed that upon introducing PMS to the
1149 Co_{SA}/MCSM_x catalyst, a new Raman peak appeared, indicating the formation of surface-activated
1150 Co_{SA}/MCSM_x-PMS complexes. Additionally, a shift in the peroxide O-O The bond peak
1151 confirmed a strong interaction between PMS molecules and the active Co-N₄ sites and adjacent
1152 carbon structures of the catalyst. After BPA was added, these metastable complexes reacted with
1153 the pollutant, leading to PMS decomposition via an electron-transfer mechanism [107]. Moreover,
1154 (Fig. 21(c)) illustrates the in-situ Raman spectra during bisphenol A (BPA) removal by Co_{SA}-
1155 NC/H₂₀MX, providing direct evidence of the catalyst activating PMS and transferring electrons
1156 during pollutant degradation. When PMS is introduced into the Co_{SA}-NC/H₂₀MX system, a new
1157 Raman peak appears at approximately 834 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the formation of a metastable

1158 $\text{Co}_{\text{SA}}\text{-NC}/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{MX-PMS}$ surface complex, indicating that PMS is successfully adsorbed and
1159 activated on the catalyst surface. Upon subsequent addition of BPA, this peak rapidly disappears,
1160 showing that the previously formed catalyst-PMS complex is consumed during the reaction. This
1161 behavior demonstrates that the activated PMS complex acts as an electron-transfer bridge,
1162 accepting electrons from BPA through the catalyst surface and thereby oxidizing BPA without
1163 relying on free radical species [101]. In situ Raman spectroscopy (Fig. 21(d,e)) of the synthesized
1164 Fe-SA/ $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$ nanohybrid showed characteristic peaks corresponding to PMS species and
1165 sulfate products, and changes in peak intensity revealed how PMS molecules interacted with the
1166 active Fe-O6 sites of Fe-SA/ $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$. A decrease in the intensity ratio of PMS-related peaks
1167 indicated faster PMS decomposition, particularly under an applied electric field, confirming that
1168 the Fe single-atom sites efficiently activated PMS on the catalyst surface [103].

1169

1170 **7. Density Functional Theory studies of various SAs@MXenes in organic pollutant** 1171 **degradation**

1172 Density functional theory (DFT) studies have demonstrated that SAs@ $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ are highly
1173 promising for degrading organic pollutants. The calculations reveal that vacancies and -O
1174 terminations on MXenes strongly stabilize isolated metal atoms (SAs), preventing aggregation and
1175 modulating their electronic states. DFT further shows that these SAs effectively adsorb and
1176 activate oxidants such as PMS and PDS, thereby lowering the O-O bond cleavage barriers and
1177 favoring non-radical pathways involving singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$), which enhance selectivity and
1178 resistance to interference. In photocatalysis, DFT calculations indicate that SAs@MXenes
1179 facilitates charge transfer and band alignment with semiconductors, thereby improving the
1180 degradation efficiency of dyes and organic molecules. Overall, vacancy engineering combined

1181 with termination control has identified DFT as the key strategy for designing efficient
1182 SAs@MXene catalysts for advanced oxidation processes [131-134].

1183 X. Guo et al. conducted DFT calculations, revealing that asymmetric CoN_1O_2 single-atom sites
1184 and adjacent Co nanoclusters confined within holey MXene structures act synergistically to
1185 enhance PMS activation. PDOS analysis revealed that $\text{Co}_{\text{SA}}\text{-NC}/\text{H}_{20}\text{MX}$ has a higher electronic
1186 density near the Fermi level than isolated Co atoms, indicating greater electron availability for
1187 catalysis. Adsorption studies demonstrated that PMS binds more strongly to dual Co sites, with a
1188 shortened O-O bond length that facilitates oxidation activation. Charge-density-difference
1189 mapping confirmed enhanced electron transfer ($0.86 e^-$) from the catalyst to PMS in the dual-site
1190 configuration, while crystal orbital Hamilton population (COHP) analysis revealed stronger Co-O
1191 bonding interactions, forming a more stable catalyst-PMS* complex (Fig. 22(a-g)). Collectively,
1192 these results indicate that dual coordination between CoN_1O_2 sites and Co nanoclusters strengthens
1193 PMS adsorption and accelerates interfacial charge transfer, enabling a nonradical electron-transfer
1194 pathway that drives the rapid and selective polymerization of organic pollutants [101].

1195 Similarly, L. Jin performed spin-polarized DFT calculations using the generalized gradient
1196 approximation (GGA) with the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) functional and D3 dispersion
1197 corrections within the VASP to elucidate the role of single-atom Cu anchored on $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene
1198 in PMS activation. The optimized structures revealed that PMS preferentially adsorbs onto isolated
1199 Cu-O_3 sites rather than directly on the MXene surface, with an O-O bond elongation from 1.42 to
1200 1.48 Å, indicating activation toward reactive species generation. Bader charge analysis confirmed
1201 net electron transfer ($0.183 e^-$) from PMS to the catalyst, initiating PMS oxidation and the
1202 subsequent formation of ROS. These electronic interactions explain the predominance of $^1\text{O}_2$ and
1203 electron-transfer pathways in the $\text{Cu}_{\text{SA}}/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ system. In contrast to the radical-dominated

1204 mechanisms observed for Cu nanoparticles or nanoclusters. Overall, DFT calculations indicate that
1205 the atomic dispersion of Cu on MXene optimizes PMS adsorption and activation energetics and
1206 promotes a nonradical, electron-transfer-mediated degradation mechanism, which accounts for the
1207 ultrafast and selective water decontamination observed experimentally [99].

1208 In another study, L. Jin employed DFT calculations using VASP with the GGA-PBE functional
1209 to investigate how the coordination environment of Cr single atoms anchored on MXene influences
1210 oxygen activation pathways. The models revealed that N-coordinated Cr-N₄ sites strongly
1211 stabilized end-on O₂ adsorption ($\Delta E = -3.86$ eV vs -2.36 eV for side-on), preventing O-O bond
1212 cleavage and promoting the formation and desorption of OOH* intermediates, a key step in
1213 selective singlet-oxygen (¹O₂) generation. Free-energy diagrams showed that the rate-determining
1214 step (OOH*→OH*) has a higher barrier on Cr-N₄ (2.19 eV) than on Cr-O₄ (1.67 eV). However,
1215 N-doping shifts the reaction pathway toward OOH* desorption rather than dissociation, thereby
1216 favoring ¹O₂ production. A volcano plot further correlated the optimized d-band center of Cr-N₄
1217 sites with their enhanced activity and selectivity (Fig. 23(a, b)). These DFT results indicate that
1218 tuning the local coordination of Cr through N-doping modulates adsorption energetics and
1219 electronic structure, resulting in selective oxygen activation [97]. Similarly, Z. Wang et al.
1220 conducted DFT calculations using spin-polarized VASP with the PBE functional to investigate the
1221 influence of interlayer confinement on atomically dispersed Cu in Ti₃C₂T_x MXene. Among the
1222 examined models (bare Cu, bare MXene, unconfined Cu-MXene, and confined Cu-MXene), the
1223 confined configuration exhibited the most exergonic PMS adsorption ($E_{\text{ads}} \approx -5.60$ eV) and the
1224 longest activated O-O bond (1.54 Å). Electron localization function and charge-density difference
1225 analyses showed pronounced charge transfer from Cu/Ti sites to the PMS oxygen atoms, creating
1226 a delocalized, redox-active environment absent in pristine MXene. This redistribution lowered the

1227 Gibbs-free-energy barrier for PMS bond cleavage from 0.144 eV in the unconfined catalyst to
1228 0.074 eV and made the final state more thermodynamically favorable (-1.43 eV) (Fig. 23(c-e)).
1229 Overall, the synergy between single-atom Cu dispersion and interlayer confinement enhances
1230 binding strength, facilitates O-O bond activation, and accelerates reactive oxygen species
1231 generation, explaining the substantially higher catalytic activity observed experimentally [100].

1232 A clear mechanistic pathway supported by experimental results was determined using DFT, as
1233 reported by F. Wang et al. A synergistic Cu-Fe/Nb₂C catalyst combining single atoms with
1234 nanoparticles was designed to regulate electronic structure, suppress HER, and achieve highly
1235 selective bromate reduction. DFT calculations were conducted using the GGA-PBE functional
1236 within the VASP framework to elucidate the electrocatalytic debromination mechanism on Cu-
1237 Fe/Nb₂C catalysts. Adsorption energy analysis showed that H* binds most strongly to
1238 Cu_{0.2}/Fe_{0.1}/Nb₂C (-0.912 eV) compared with pristine Nb₂C (-0.193 eV), Fe_{0.1}/Nb₂C (-0.337 eV),
1239 and Cu_{0.2}/Nb₂C (-0.601 eV), confirming that the bimetallic synergy stabilizes H* intermediates
1240 (Fig. 24(a)). TDOS calculations revealed that Cu and Fe incorporation shifted the d-band center
1241 closer to the Fermi level, weakening H*- metal interactions and reducing the adsorption energy
1242 barrier (Fig. 24(b)). Charge-density-difference mapping further showed electronic-cloud bridges
1243 between Fe₂O₃ NPs and Nb₂C, indicating strong electronic metal-support interactions (EMSI). In
1244 (Fig. 24(c)) Fermi-level shifts indicate progressive upward movement from Nb₂C → Fe/Nb₂C →
1245 Cu/Nb₂C → Cu-Fe/Nb₂C, confirming stronger electronic interactions in the bimetallic system.
1246 Also, reaction pathway structures and energy profiles (Fig. 24(d-f)) show that Cu-Fe/Nb₂C
1247 stabilizes the 2H*, transition state, and H₂ formation steps more effectively than Fe-only Nb₂C.
1248 Notably, the energy barrier for hydrogen evolution was higher on Cu_{0.2}/Fe_{0.1}/Nb₂C (1.76 eV) than

1249 on Fe_{0.1}/Nb₂C (1.06 eV), indicating suppressed hydrogen evolution and enhanced retention of
1250 adsorbed H* species [135].

1251 Furthermore, M. Li et al. employed the GGA-PBE functional with projector augmented-wave
1252 (PAW) pseudopotentials to describe core electrons. DFT calculations were performed to explain
1253 the selective generation of superoxide radicals ($\cdot\text{O}_2^-$) in the Co_{SA}-N-Ti₃C₂T_x/PMS system. A Co-
1254 N₂O₃ single-atom site constructed based on XAFS-derived geometry exhibited a formation energy
1255 of -15.77 eV, confirming thermodynamic stability. Mulliken charge analysis revealed that nitrogen
1256 coordination reduced the positive charge on Co to +0.20, enhancing electron donation compared
1257 to Co-O₃ sites. Adsorption studies indicated that hydroxyl oxygen in PMS binds most strongly,
1258 with favorable free-energy profiles for both adsorption and desorption, and an elongated O-O
1259 bond, establishing this site as the PMS activation center. Electron-density-difference mapping
1260 showed that PMS gained 0.31 e⁻ and acetaminophen (ACE) gained 0.35 e⁻ upon adsorption, while
1261 dissolved O₂ accepted electrons to generate $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ radicals. Among the competing adsorbates, PMS
1262 exhibited the most favorable adsorption energy (\approx -1.87 eV). However, electron-rich ACE
1263 contributed additional electrons that facilitated O₂ reduction in the electron-deficient Co-N₂O₃
1264 region. This mechanism, characterized by strong PMS anchoring, electron accumulation, and
1265 pollutant-assisted O₂ reduction, accounts for the experimentally observed rapid self-coupling of
1266 phenolic pollutants driven by $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ radicals [98].

1267 In a similar approach, optimized Co-N₂O₁ models revealed pronounced charge polarization
1268 and a 1.05 e⁻ electron transfer from the Co center toward the axial O-MXene ligand, leaving the
1269 cobalt atom more electron-depleted than the planar Co-N₄ configuration. Bader charge analysis
1270 confirmed the higher oxidation state of Co in the N₂O₁ site, while differential charge-density maps
1271 (Fig. 25(a,b)) visualized electron depletion around the Co core. The Ultraviolet photoelectron

1272 spectroscopy (UPS) data (Fig. 25(c)) show that Co_{SA}-N₂O₁/MXene exhibits a higher valance band
1273 edge (E_v) relative to Co_{SA}-N₄, indicating improved electronic structure and easier electron
1274 excitation, which benefits catalytic reactions. PDOS analysis showed that the Co 3*d*-band center
1275 shifted closer to the Fermi level (-1.29 eV compared with -2.69 eV for Co-N₄), thereby enhancing
1276 the adsorption and charge-transfer kinetics of PMS (Fig 25(d)). Adsorption calculations indicated
1277 that PMS binds most favorably through its terminal oxygen ($E_{\text{ads}} \approx -1.56$ eV) and accepts ~ 0.8 e⁻
1278 from the catalyst, whereas the electron flow in Co-N₄ reverses, promoting radical-mediated
1279 pathways (Fig. 25(e)). Free-energy diagrams (Fig. 25(f)) further demonstrated that the key O-O
1280 cleavage and ¹O₂-forming steps require lower activation barriers on the Co-N₂O₁ surface (+1.29
1281 eV) than on Co-N₄ (>2 eV). Collectively, these results explain the experimentally observed
1282 transition from $\cdot\text{OH}/\text{SO}_4\cdot^-$ radical generation to highly selective singlet-oxygen formation in the
1283 Co_{SA}-N₂O₁/MXene-PMS system [83].

1284

1285 **8. Machine learning for catalyst design: A data-driven approach**

1286 The application of ML in catalysis is a rapidly growing field that primarily focuses on high-
1287 throughput computational screening of relatively simple, well-defined reactions such as HER and
1288 CO₂RR. While MXenes have been shown to degrade pollutants, most studies use MXenes as
1289 components in composite materials rather than as supports for atomically dispersed catalysts. The
1290 computational and theoretical design of SAs@MXenes remains an emerging research frontier,
1291 with applications so far largely restricted to energy-related electrocatalysis rather than
1292 environmental remediation. Designing catalysts for complex, multi-component degradation
1293 processes in heterogeneous water matrices using ML is computationally demanding. Artificial
1294 intelligence (AI), particularly ML, is transforming catalyst discovery by shifting from traditional

1295 trial-and-error approaches to a data-driven workflow (Fig. 26) [136]. ML models efficiently
1296 identify patterns in catalytic datasets, enabling accurate prediction of material properties and
1297 prioritization of experimental efforts. The intelligence-guided framework accelerates discovery,
1298 reduces resource consumption, and minimizes reliance on costly theoretical calculations. MXene-
1299 based SACs feature diverse structural and compositional variables, including surface terminations
1300 (O, F, S, and Cl), doped transition metals ($3d$, $4d$, and $5d$ orbitals), variable compositions, defect
1301 structures, and surface vacancies. Exhaustively evaluating these parameters using DFT is
1302 expensive, prompting the integration of ML. In this context, the ML workflow typically follows a
1303 systematic multi-phase approach. Large datasets are first generated, often from DFT or other high-
1304 throughput computational simulations, that contain key information on electronic-structure
1305 properties such as d-band centers, Bader charges, and adsorption or binding energies for various
1306 adsorbates. For example, M. Huang et al. developed a publicly available SAC database containing
1307 1,197 entries, including DFT-calculated electronic-structure and binding-energy data. This dataset
1308 served as the foundation for subsequent ML-based prediction of catalytic activity. Once
1309 constructed, various regression algorithms such as Support Vector Regression (SVR), Random
1310 Forest Regression (RFR), and Extreme Gradient Boosting Regression (XGBR) are trained to
1311 predict catalyst performance. In one study, the XGBR model (Fig. 27) achieved the highest
1312 predictive accuracy, effectively forecasting the electronic structure and oxygen adsorption energies
1313 of catalysts. These trained models were subsequently integrated into frameworks such as catalytic
1314 volcano models [137]. The success of such data-driven methods heavily relies on the availability
1315 of large, high-quality, and reliable datasets. The recent development of specialized databases, even
1316 for targeted reactions such as NO and Hg(0) oxidation, has enabled the rapid screening and
1317 discovery of highly active catalysts.

1318 Y. Zhang et al. demonstrated the integration of ML with DFT to accelerate the discovery of
1319 efficient SAs@MXenes catalysts. Their study used ML to evaluate the ORR activity of various
1320 MXene-supported SACs to identify critical structural and electronic descriptors influencing
1321 catalytic behavior. Seven regression models, namely Gradient Boosting Regression (GBR),
1322 AdaBoost Regression (ABR), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBR), Random Forest Regression
1323 (RFR), Light Gradient Boosting (LightGBM), Decision Tree Regression (DTR), and Multilayer
1324 Perceptron Regression (MLPR) were applied to correlate catalyst features with calculated ORR
1325 overpotentials. The GBR model achieved the highest predictive accuracy, yielding an R^2 value of
1326 0.95 and an RMSE of 0.23, demonstrating excellent agreement between the DFT-calculated and
1327 ML-predicted values. Using the SISO algorithm, composite descriptors (D_1 , D_2 , D_3) were derived
1328 by combining electron affinity, ionization energy, Bader charge, electronegativity, and the number
1329 of d-electrons. Shapely Additive Explanation (SHAP) analysis further revealed that the Bader
1330 charge, d-electron count, and feature D were the most influential factors determining catalytic
1331 activity. This approach identified Pd/Ti₂NO₂ and Rh/Ti₂NO₂ as highly active catalysts,
1332 highlighting the potential of ML-assisted, data-driven methods for accurate and efficient catalyst
1333 prediction [138].

1334 The ML framework demonstrated in this study can be extended to the degradation of organic
1335 pollutants. Similar to ORR systems, ML can correlate the structural, electronic, and adsorption
1336 properties of catalysts with degradation efficiency to identify optimal materials for decomposing
1337 compounds such as dyes, phenols, and bisphenol A. By training ML models on DFT-derived or
1338 experimental datasets, parameters such as adsorption energy, charge transfer capacity, HOMO-
1339 LUMO gap, and oxygen vacancy concentration can be optimized to predict degradation rates and
1340 mechanisms. Feature engineering methods similar to SISO facilitate the identification of key

1341 descriptors linking catalyst structure to reactivity, enabling the rational design of MXene-based or
1342 single-atom catalysts for photocatalytic and electrocatalytic degradation.

1343 Although literature on ML studies involving SAs@MXenes for organic pollutant remediation
1344 remains limited, W. Wang *et al.* demonstrated the effective removal of chlortetracycline
1345 hydrochloride (CTC) using MXene, achieving remarkable results (Fig. 28(a)). Machine learning
1346 played a central role by enabling precise optimization of the preparation conditions of TBAOH-
1347 intercalated Nb₂CT_x MXene through two hybrid computational models: a Backpropagation Neural
1348 Network coupled with a Genetic Algorithm (BPNN-GA) and a Random Forest integrated with a
1349 Genetic Algorithm (RF-GA). These models were designed to capture the complex nonlinear
1350 relationships between key synthesis parameters, namely, TBAOH concentration, reaction time,
1351 and reaction temperature, and their collective influence on the CTC removal efficiency. Despite
1352 the limited size of the experimental dataset, both ML models demonstrated strong predictive
1353 accuracy, effectively reducing the number of trial-and-error experiments required. Among the two,
1354 the BPNN-GA model exhibited superior statistical performance, as evidenced by higher
1355 coefficients of determination and significantly lower error indicators, including MAE, MSE, and
1356 RMSE (Fig. 28(b-d)). This model identified the optimal preparation conditions as 1% TBAOH
1357 concentration, 4 h reaction time, and 25 °C, which were experimentally validated to achieve a high
1358 CTC removal efficiency of approximately 89%. Under these optimized conditions, the resulting
1359 TBAOH-Nb₂CT_x MXene exhibited enhanced physicochemical properties, including expanded
1360 interlayer spacing, increased specific surface area, and improved accessibility of adsorption sites,
1361 collectively contributing to its strong adsorption capability. The adsorption behavior followed
1362 pseudo-second-order kinetics and was well fitted by the Freundlich isotherm, highlighting the
1363 dominance of chemisorption and multilayer adsorption on heterogeneous surfaces. The ML-

1364 optimized material exhibited excellent recyclability and structural stability over multiple
1365 adsorption–desorption cycles, reinforcing its practical applicability. Overall, the integration of
1366 machine learning not only accelerated the optimization workflow and reduced research costs but
1367 also strengthened the understanding of synthesis–structure–performance relationships. This work
1368 demonstrates that ML-assisted predictive modelling is a powerful and generalizable strategy for
1369 designing advanced MXene-based materials for environmental remediation [139].

1370 Furthermore, Machine learning was used to develop quantitative descriptors that link MXene-
1371 supported SACs to the adsorption energies of atomic and molecular intermediates. The sure
1372 independence screening and sparsifying operator (SISSO) algorithm was used to fit adsorption
1373 energy data obtained from DFT calculations (Fig. 29(a)). Five primary atomic features, atomic
1374 mass (M), electronegativity (χ), electron affinity (EA), first ionization energy (EI), and valence
1375 electron number (Ne) were selected after Pearson correlation filtering (>90% correlation
1376 removed). For atomic intermediates adsorbed on M-Ti₂C (O, N, C, and H), SISSO models of
1377 increasing dimensionality (1D, 2D, and 3D) were constructed. The 3D descriptors exhibited the
1378 highest predictive accuracy, with coefficients of determination (R^2) of 0.796 (O), 0.960 (N), 0.970
1379 (C), and 0.876 (H) when compared with DFT-calculated adsorption energies (Fig.29(b,c)). Among
1380 these, nitrogen and carbon adsorption showed strong agreement, indicating strong reliability of the
1381 descriptors. For molecular intermediates (NO, CO, N₂, NNH, NH₃, and H₂O) adsorbed on M-
1382 Ti₂CO₂, SISSO-derived descriptors successfully reproduced adsorption energy trends across
1383 different dopant metals (Fig.29 (d,e)). The models captured variations in adsorption strength
1384 arising from changes in valence electron number and electronic structure, enabling rapid screening
1385 of catalytically active sites without further DFT calculations. These results demonstrate that

1386 SISSO-based ML can accurately reproduce adsorption energetics and provide transferable, low-
1387 dimensional descriptors for MXene-based catalyst design [140].

1388 Machine learning models were trained to predict the adsorption energies (E_{ads}) and diffusion
1389 energy barriers (E_{b}) of single transition metal atoms supported on MXenes using a dataset
1390 comprising 1,620 DFT-calculated systems (Fig. 30(a)). Twelve supervised regression algorithms
1391 were evaluated using 30-fold cross-validation, with performance assessed by mean absolute error
1392 (MAE) and coefficient of determination (R^2). Among all models, the random forest regressor
1393 (RFR) consistently showed the highest predictive accuracy. For predicting adsorption energy, the
1394 optimized RFR model achieved an MAE of 0.21 eV and an R^2 value of 0.99, approaching the
1395 intrinsic uncertainty of DFT calculations. After descriptor dimensionality reduction, the MAE
1396 slightly increased to 0.25 eV, while preserving strong linearity. Feature importance analysis
1397 identified the cohesive energy of the single atom (E_{coh}) as the dominant descriptor, contributing
1398 ~81% to the prediction accuracy, followed by the d-electron count and MXene metal radius. For
1399 diffusion energy barriers, the RFR model yielded an MAE of 0.07 eV and an R^2 of 0.72 across the
1400 full dataset (Fig. 30(b)). When restricting the analysis to systems with $E_{\text{b}} < 0.4$ eV ($\approx 85\%$ of cases),
1401 the MAE further decreased to 0.05 eV, indicating improved reliability in experimentally relevant
1402 regimes. External validation on unseen MXenes (M_5X_4) yielded an R^2 of 0.994 and an MAE of
1403 0.17 eV, confirming the robustness and transferability of the ML framework. The parity plots in
1404 Fig. 30(c) and (d) show that predictions for E_{ads} from RFR are highly accurate, with only a few
1405 N-based MXene outliers and no influence from 3d, 4d, or 5d TMs [141].

1406 In another study, Q. Liu et al. employed machine learning to transform the optical responses of an
1407 MXene-based biosensor into an accurate, user-independent quantitative tool for ochratoxin A
1408 (OTA), a toxic organic pollutant. A fully connected artificial neural network (FCANN) was

1409 developed by using RGB values extracted from fluorescence and colorimetric images acquired
1410 through a smartphone-based platform (Fig. 31(a)). For the fluorescence-based FCANN, the
1411 predicted values had an R^2 of 0.9997, while the colorimetric FCANN had an R^2 of 0.9995. These
1412 results demonstrate excellent prediction accuracy and robustness. The effective detection ranges
1413 of the ML-assisted model were 500-9000 pg mL^{-1} for fluorescence and 500-8000 pg mL^{-1} for
1414 colorimetry, with corresponding limits of detection of 11.70 pg mL^{-1} and 5.69 pg mL^{-1} , respectively.
1415 (Fig. 31(b-g)), Created with the matplotlib tool, illustrates the FCANN model's training process
1416 and predicted performance for C_{OTA} . Specifically, (Fig. 31d, e) show that the FCANN model's
1417 fluorescence and colorimetric channels exhibit stable loss error values after 60 and 90 generations,
1418 indicating excellent convergence. Importantly, although the ML-derived LOD values were slightly
1419 higher than those obtained from direct instrumental calibration, the ML-assisted approach offered
1420 superior reliability, reduced human error, and improved adaptability to real-sample imaging
1421 conditions. By learning nonlinear relationships between RGB values and OTA concentration, the
1422 FCANN minimized signal fluctuations caused by lighting variations and matrix effects. These
1423 experimental results confirm that machine learning significantly enhances the quantitative
1424 accuracy and practical usability of the biosensor, enabling rapid, on-site OTA detection without
1425 specialized analytical equipment [142].

1426 These ML-driven strategies not only accelerate catalyst screening but also provide mechanistic
1427 insight into pollutant adsorption and radical generation, enabling the development of highly
1428 efficient, stable, and cost-effective catalysts for environmental remediation. Table 7 and Table 8
1429 summarize the types of ML models and datasets used in catalyst design, as well as their
1430 applications for degrading organic pollutants.

1431

1432 **9. Molecular dynamics of SAs@MXenes**

1433 MD simulations play a vital role in investigating SAs@MXenes catalysts, providing dynamic
1434 insights beyond static calculations [104]. They are particularly valuable for assessing thermal
1435 stability, as they help determine whether SAs such as Fe, Co, Ni, or Cu remain firmly anchored on
1436 MXene surfaces under varying temperature conditions. MD also enables examination of bonding
1437 dynamics, offering a time-resolved perspective on interactions between metal atoms and surface
1438 sites, including M-C, M-O, and M-N bonds. Furthermore, MD captures the catalytic environment
1439 more realistically by incorporating solvation effects, reactant diffusion, and local structural
1440 fluctuations, which are often neglected in static DFT calculations [143]. Importantly, MD
1441 simulations can trace the behavior of reaction intermediates, including the adsorption and
1442 desorption of CO₂, H^{*}, O₂, and pollutants such as antibiotics or dyes, thereby providing a
1443 comprehensive understanding of catalytic processes. MD simulations of MXene-based SACs are
1444 performed using several approaches, each offering distinct insights into their catalytic behavior.
1445 Ab initio molecular dynamics (AIMD), based on DFT, is commonly employed to evaluate the
1446 intrinsic thermal stability of MXene SACs (typically 300–1000 K) and to examine whether single
1447 atoms migrate, cluster, or remain anchored at their active sites [144]. Classical MD, though less
1448 frequently applied due to the chemical complexity of SACs, uses force fields to simulate larger
1449 systems, such as pollutant-MXene interactions in aqueous media. Reactive force field MD
1450 (ReaxFF), on the other hand, is particularly valuable for modeling bond-breaking and bond-
1451 forming events during catalytic, redox, or pollutant-degradation reactions, allowing exploration of
1452 longer, more realistic time scales than AIMD [145]. Findings from these simulations have yielded
1453 key insights. AIMD studies confirm that most transition-metal SACs on MXenes remain stable up
1454 to ~800 K, preventing aggregation. Solvent interactions observed in MD highlight the stabilizing

1455 role of water molecules on catalytic intermediates, while classical MD helps map the diffusion
1456 pathways of molecules such as CO₂, O₂, or organic pollutants toward active sites. Combined AIMD
1457 and electronic-structure analyses further reveal dynamic charge transfer between the single-atom
1458 centers and MXene supports. These results have been successfully applied to environmental
1459 applications, including the degradation of organic pollutants such as sulfamethoxazole, bisphenol-
1460 A, and carbamazepine. ReaxFF-based molecular dynamics simulations have also been
1461 instrumental in capturing bond-breaking and bond-forming processes of PFAS molecules under
1462 extreme conditions that are difficult to probe experimentally (Fig. 32).

1463 Unlike the classical MD, which treats chemical bonds as fixed, the ReaxFF method
1464 incorporates bond-order concepts and dynamic electronic interactions. This enables realistic
1465 simulation of stepwise C-F and C-C bond cleavage, radical formation, and subsequent
1466 recombination during pyrolysis. This capability provided mechanistic insight into head-tail
1467 dissociation, radical intermediates (CF₃, CF₂, CF), and preferential CO formation, which explains
1468 why ultrasonic nanobubble implosions achieve more than 98% defluorination without generating
1469 stable, toxic byproducts. Moreover, the simulations reproduced kinetic parameters ($E_a \approx 58.9$ KJ
1470 mol⁻¹) in close agreement with experimental data, confirming the reliability of ReaxFF in modeling
1471 PFAS chemistry. By bridging the gap between the accuracy of DFT and the large-scale stability of
1472 classical MD, ReaxFF enabled a detailed molecular-level understanding of PFAS mineralization
1473 [146].

1474 Z. Wang et al. employed MD simulations to elucidate the influence of interlayer
1475 nanoconfinement within Cu_SA/MXene nanochannels on the transport and spatial distribution of
1476 reactants, particularly PMS oxidant and BPA pollutant molecules. A model with an interlayer
1477 spacing of ≈ 1.37 nm, consistent with TEM observations, was compared with the wider channels

1478 (5 and 10nm). The MD simulations revealed that the narrower channels substantially enriched
1479 PMS and BPA molecules near the Cu active sites, forming a localized reaction zone that promoted
1480 rapid PMS activation into reactive oxygen species (ROS). This enrichment resulted from a
1481 combination of geometric confinement, electrostatic interactions, surface complexation, and
1482 hydrogen bonding, which collectively enhanced molecular localization and contact frequency.
1483 Quantitatively, mean square displacement (MSD) analysis showed shortened diffusion paths and
1484 accelerated molecular transport in the confined system (Fig. 33(a-d)), while mass-density profiles
1485 indicated a significantly higher PMS concentration ($\approx 0.9 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ at 1.37 nm compared with 0.45
1486 and 0.2 g cm^{-3} for 5 and 10 nm channels) near the catalytic interface [100]. Overall, these findings
1487 demonstrate that nanoconfinement accelerates diffusion and sustains high local reactant
1488 concentrations, thereby enhancing the efficiency of ROS generation. The MD insights complement
1489 experimental evidence, confirming that structural confinement and single-atom Cu sites
1490 synergistically improve PMS activation and pollutant degradation by optimizing both mass
1491 transport and catalytic microenvironments. Furthermore, Y. Wang et al. employed the MD
1492 simulations to investigate the adsorption and diffusion behavior of bisphenol A (BPA) in aqueous
1493 environments across $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{O}_x$, $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2(\text{OH})_x$, and $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{F}_x$ MXene membranes with different
1494 interlayer spacings at 298 K. A membrane solution vacuum model was constructed, where
1495 BPA/H₂O mixtures migrated from the feed zone toward the membrane under NVT conditions (Fig.
1496 34(a)). The interlayer spacings were 6, 8, 10, 12, and 14 Å, and the materials were designated as
1497 P6, P8, P10, P12 and P14, respectively. Fig. 34(b-d)) shows the effects of MD simulation on BPA
1498 concentrations across all membranes. The membrane was located between the green lines, with
1499 the solution region to the left and the permeation zone to the right. After 10 ns

1500 in MD simulations of MXenes with varying interlayer spacings, it was shown that BPA could
1501 permeate the smallest voids of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{O}_x$, $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2(\text{OH})_x$, and $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{F}_x$, corresponding to P8, P6, and
1502 P12, respectively. (Fig. 34 (e-g)) depicts the MSD-versus-time curve for BPA in MXenes with
1503 varying interlayer spacings. The results revealed that water molecules preferentially occupied
1504 narrow interlayer voids, requiring larger interlayer spacing for effective BPA adsorption than under
1505 gas-phase conditions. $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2(\text{OH})_x$ exhibited the smallest critical interlayer spacing for BPA entry,
1506 followed by $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{O}_x$ and $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{O}_x$ and $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{F}_x$. Concentration profiles showed that BPA was
1507 strongly retained within the interlayers of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{O}_x$ and $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2(\text{OH})_x$, whereas $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{F}_x$ allowed
1508 partial penetration of BPA into the permeate zone at larger spacings, indicating weaker interactions.
1509 Mean square displacement analysis confirmed reduced BPA mobility upon adsorption, with
1510 diffusion coefficients following the order $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{F}_x > \text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{O}_x > \text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2(\text{OH})_x$, demonstrating that
1511 hydroxyl- and oxygen-terminated MXenes provide stronger confinement and superior adsorption
1512 stability for BPA in aqueous systems [147].

1513 Active-learning potential molecular dynamics (AlpMD) simulations were employed to
1514 investigate the oxidation behaviour of MXenes in aqueous environments at nanosecond timescales
1515 with near ab initio accuracy. Using a neural-network potential trained through an iterative active-
1516 learning scheme, large-scale $\text{V}_2\text{CO}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ systems containing up to thousands of water molecules
1517 were simulated under NVT conditions. The final snapshots are given in (Fig. 35(a)). vanadium
1518 oxides on the surface of V_2CO_2 in all H_2O systems. The MD results revealed that MXene oxidation
1519 proceeds spontaneously via water adsorption at surface metal sites, followed by O-H bond
1520 cleavage and proton release, resulting in the formation of stable surface vanadium oxides. (Fig.
1521 35(b)) shows a very scattered distribution of vanadium oxides, with neighboring V atoms not
1522 becoming vanadium oxides simultaneously. Furthermore, as illustrated in (Fig. 35(c)), the

1523 outermost O atom of vanadium oxides can form hydrogen bonds with two water molecules. To
1524 verify the vanadium oxide protection mechanism, the six closest V atoms to each vanadium oxide
1525 are considered protected. (Fig. 35(d-e)) illustrates the average distance (VO) and likelihood of H₂O
1526 physical adsorption (VO distance < 3.60 Å) on shielded and stable V atoms. Protected vanadium
1527 atoms have a longer average distance (VO) than stable vanadium atoms, indicating a lower
1528 likelihood of physical adsorption by H₂O. Oxidation kinetics exhibited two regimes: an initial
1529 rapid stage and a subsequent saturation stage, with the oxidation rate decaying exponentially over
1530 time, consistent with experimental observations. Increasing the thickness of the water layer
1531 reduced the oxidation rate by restricting water mobility within hydrogen-bond networks. Proton
1532 transport followed the Eigen-Zundel-Eigel mechanism, and the generated protons, together with
1533 surface oxides, formed a protective hydration structure that inhibited further water attack. These
1534 findings demonstrate that MXene oxidation in aqueous systems is a self-limiting, kinetically
1535 controlled process governed by proton dynamics and oxide-induced surface passivation [148]. In
1536 another study, classical molecular dynamics simulations were conducted to elucidate the
1537 adsorption behavior of ciprofloxacin (CIP) and methyl orange (MO) on MXene/ZIF-8 hybrid
1538 nanocomposites (MX@ZIF, MXO@ZIF, and MXOH@ZIF) in aqueous environments. The nano
1539 substrates were centered in the simulation box, with pollutant molecules at the top and bottom
1540 (Fig. 36(a)). Simulations over 150 ns revealed spontaneous adsorption of both pollutants onto all
1541 substrates, with a significantly stronger affinity for hydroxyl-terminated MXOH@ZIF. The
1542 interaction energy analysis showed that van der Waals forces dominate the adsorption process,
1543 contributing more substantially than electrostatic interactions, while the presence of -O and -OH
1544 terminal groups enhanced overall binding strength. The MXOH@ZIF systems exhibited the most
1545 negative adsorption energies (\approx -250 KJ/mol for CIP and -200KJ/mol for MO), the highest number

1546 of pollutant-substrate contacts, and the shortest equilibrium adsorption distances. Radial
1547 distribution function analysis indicated higher RDF peak intensities for MXOH@ZIF, confirming
1548 stronger interfacial confinement (Fig. 36(b, c)). Mean square displacement results further
1549 demonstrated reduced mobility of CIP and MO on MXOH@ZIF, with the lowest diffusion
1550 coefficients among all systems. Hydrogen-bond analysis revealed a decrease in pollutant-substrate
1551 hydrogen bonding over time, indicating stable adsorption. Overall, the MD results confirm that the
1552 synergistic integration of ZIF-8 with hydroxyl-functionalized MXene significantly enhances the
1553 adsorption stability and efficiency of organic dyes and antibiotics in aqueous systems [149].

1554

1555 **10. Conclusions**

1556 SAs@MXenes are a transformative class of environmental materials that combine the atomic-level
1557 precision and catalytic efficiency of isolated metal atoms with the intrinsic advantages of MXenes,
1558 including high electrical conductivity, layered structure, surface hydrophilicity, abundant defects,
1559 and diverse functional groups. These combined features enable the precise modulation of the
1560 electronic structure, coordination environment, and catalytic activity of single atoms, significantly
1561 enhancing their performance in redox-driven pollutant degradation. A wide range of advanced
1562 synthesis strategies, such as defect engineering, heteroatom coordination, axial coordination
1563 control, and UV-assisted atom immobilization, have been developed to produce
1564 thermodynamically stable, atomically dispersed metal centers that do not aggregate. These
1565 methods strengthen metal-support interactions, which are crucial for catalytic durability and
1566 preventing metal leaching under complex aqueous conditions.

1567 Cutting-edge characterization techniques provide atomic-level insight into the structural and
1568 coordination environments of SAs@MXenes. HAADF-STEM visualizes the atomic dispersion of

1569 isolated metal atoms such as Fe, Co, Cu, or Ni on MXene nanosheets, while STEM-EELS mapping
1570 verifies the uniform distribution of SAs and identifies structural defects on MXenes. XPS,
1571 XANES, and EXAFS analyses elucidate the oxidation states and coordination chemistry between
1572 SAs and MXenes supports, revealing that these atoms are typically anchored onto $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXenes
1573 through strong M-O-Ti or M-C-Ti coordination. This coordination stabilizes metal atoms, inhibits
1574 leaching, and promotes efficient electron transfer during catalytic reactions. Furthermore, Raman
1575 spectroscopy detects shifts in Ti-C and Ti-O vibrational modes, reflecting lattice modification upon
1576 SA incorporation, while EPR spectroscopy identifies reactive oxygen species formed during
1577 pollutant oxidation, confirming radical-mediated degradation mechanisms.

1578 Compared with conventional catalyst supports such as graphene, $g-C_3N_4$, and metal oxides,
1579 SAs@MXenes exhibit significantly higher catalytic efficiency and durability. This superiority
1580 arises from their intrinsic metallic conductivity, hydrophilicity, vacancy density, and abundant
1581 surface terminations, which enable rapid electron migration and enhance the kinetics of the
1582 interfacial redox reaction. The two-dimensional multilayered structure provides a high density of
1583 exposed active sites and facilitates close interaction with pollutant molecules. Additionally, the
1584 tunable surface chemistry of MXenes allows the modulation of single-atom oxidation states and
1585 coordination geometries, thereby promoting selective adsorption and activation of organic
1586 contaminants. Consequently, SAs@MXenes demonstrates remarkable activity, stability, and
1587 recyclability in advanced oxidation processes, including Fenton-like, photocatalytic, and
1588 peroxymonosulfate activation systems for the degradation of organic pollutants.

1589 Mechanistically, single-atom centers act as highly active catalytic sites that efficiently activate
1590 oxidants such as PMS and persulfate (PS). These activation processes generate both radical and
1591 non-radical pathways, enabling the rapid, selective, and energy-efficient degradation of organic

1592 pollutants, pharmaceuticals, dyes, and endocrine-disrupting chemicals. Meanwhile, the MXene
1593 substrate actively participates in redox cycling, promoting active-site regeneration and sustaining
1594 catalytic performance across varying pH conditions and real wastewater environments. Beyond
1595 experimental progress, computational approaches, including DFT, ML, and MD simulations, serve
1596 as powerful tools for elucidating reaction mechanisms, adsorption dynamics, and pollutant-catalyst
1597 interactions. ML models accelerate catalyst screening and optimization, while DFT calculations
1598 reveal electronic structure modulation and energy barriers, providing a foundation for rational
1599 catalyst design. Overall, these advancements position SAs@MXenes as next-generation materials
1600 for environmental remediation, offering outstanding efficiency, stability, and scalability for water
1601 purification, energy-efficient detoxification, and sustainable environmental technologies.

1602

1603 10.1. Future prospects

1604 MXenes have emerged as advanced materials due to their exceptional electronic tunability and
1605 strong metal–support interactions. These unique characteristics make them excellent candidates
1606 for coordinating various SA, dual-atom, and multi-atom species in photocatalytic degradation of
1607 organic pollutants, electrocatalytic wastewater detoxification, selective adsorption of contaminants
1608 such as pesticides, pharmaceuticals, dyes, and industrial chemicals, and in biotechnology and
1609 energy-related applications.

1610 To monitor reaction intermediates in real time and elucidate catalytic pathways, in
1611 situ/operando spectroscopic techniques are highly desirable. In this review, we have discussed in
1612 situ Raman spectroscopy for investigating SAs@MXenes during the catalytic detoxification of
1613 organic pollutants. However, greater emphasis on advanced techniques such as XAS
1614 (XANES/EXAFS) and diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFT) is

1615 essential. These techniques are widely used in electrochemical and photochemical energy-
1616 conversion studies to identify active sites, monitor dynamic structural evolution, and define
1617 reaction pathways under working conditions. Such mechanisms are crucial for correlating
1618 experimental observations with DFT calculations and for reliable reaction models.

1619 The integration of DFT and ML-driven predictive models transforms catalyst design by
1620 enabling the rapid identification of efficient active sites, elucidation of stable coordination
1621 geometries, and accurate prediction of pollutant adsorption pathways at the atomic scale. This
1622 computational-experimental synergy reduces the need for extensive trial-and-error experiments,
1623 facilitating the rational design of high-performance catalysts. Future research may focus on
1624 developing self-learning algorithms that autonomously optimize catalyst structures for specific
1625 environmental reactions. Additionally, coupling theoretical screening with experimental synthesis
1626 can create a high-throughput discovery framework that accelerates the development of scalable
1627 and cost-effective MXene-based single-atom catalysts.

1628 Exploring axial coordination tuning and incorporating non-metal heteroatoms (e.g., N, S, P,
1629 and B) into MXene frameworks offers promising strategies for modifying the local electronic
1630 environment. Adjusting the d-band center and charge-density distribution around single-atom
1631 active sites can enhance the precision of adsorption energy and improve catalytic selectivity and
1632 redox reactivity. These design principles can guide the development of catalysts that selectively
1633 target specific pollutants or reaction pathways in complex aqueous environments.

1634 The inherent structural flexibility of MXenes enables the construction of hybrid architectures
1635 incorporating polymers, membranes, and carbonaceous nanostructures, particularly suited for
1636 single-atom MXene catalysts. These hybrid systems combine the high conductivity and atomic
1637 anchoring ability of MXenes with the mechanical strength and surface tunability of organic or

1638 carbon supports. Such architectures effectively prevent the migration or aggregation of isolated
1639 metal atoms, thereby improving stability, reusability, and multifunctionality. Consequently, the
1640 single-atom active sites remain intact under real operational conditions. Additionally, this approach
1641 facilitates the development of modular catalytic materials that can be integrated into continuous-
1642 flow, electrochemical membrane, or photoelectrocatalytic treatment systems. These innovations
1643 advance the practical application of SAs@MXenes catalysts for large-scale pollutant
1644 detoxification and energy conversion.

1645 Scalability, cost, and environmental footprint, which are critical considerations for the practical
1646 deployment of SAs@MXenes. Although MXenes can be synthesized in large quantities, current
1647 production routes often rely on hazardous etchants (fluoride-based chemicals), which increase
1648 cost, complicate scale-up, and raise environmental concerns related to waste management. From a
1649 cost perspective, using ultralow metal loadings in SAs significantly reduces noble-metal
1650 consumption, partially offsetting the cost of synthesis. SAs@MXenes offer advantages through
1651 high atomic efficiency, enhanced catalytic activity, and longer operational lifetimes, which can
1652 reduce energy input and material use per unit performance; however, greener, fluoride-free MXene
1653 synthesis routes and scalable, solvent-efficient single-atom anchoring strategies are essential to
1654 minimize the overall environmental footprint and enable sustainable large-scale applications.

1655 Collectively, these advancements position SAs@MXenes catalysts as next-generation
1656 materials for sustainable, efficient, and selective removal of emerging contaminants from complex
1657 environmental systems, with strong potential for real-water implementation and practical
1658 scalability. Fig. 37 presents a schematic overview of future prospects, underscoring the importance
1659 of developing advanced synthesis strategies to support large-scale production while maintaining
1660 economic feasibility and environmental sustainability. From a technological standpoint, the

1661 incorporation of artificial intelligence, particularly machine-learning methodologies, offers
1662 substantial potential for rationally designing next-generation single-atom catalysts and optimizing
1663 their performance for targeted industrial applications. Overall, the expansion of SAC-based
1664 technologies across diverse sectors, including catalysis, biotechnology, and environmental
1665 detoxification, continues to advance rapidly.

1666

1667 **Authors contributions**

1668 K.K. and EV L. wrote the original draft. S.V. conceptualized the study, contributed to writing the
1669 original draft, and supervised the preparation of the review manuscript. S.V., K. P., D. K., and K.
1670 S. performed formal analysis, review, and editing. R. V. J. and N.V.V.J. supervised the preparation
1671 of the original draft. A. B., M. Y., and R.Z. provided supervision, funding, and critical editing of
1672 the original draft. All authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

1673

1674 **Declaration of competing interest**

1675 The authors declared no conflict of interest

1676

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1690

1691 **Data availability**

1692 No data were generated for the production of this work.

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2201 **Schemes and Figures**

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2204 **Scheme 1.** (a) Timeline illustrating the year-wise advancements in the development of
 2205 SAs@MXene catalysts for the treatment of organic pollutants; (b) Representative toxic organic
 2206 molecules.
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2209 **Scheme 2.** Schematic representation of SAs@MXene for organic molecule detoxification,
 2210 advanced characterization, DFT, ML, and MD studies.

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2213 **Fig. 1.** (a) Schematic representation of Pt single-atom construction on monolayer $Ti_3C_2T_x$ reprinted
 2214 with permission from [77]; (b) fabrication of $Pt-V_2CT_x$ nanosheets, reprinted with permission from
 2215 [78]; (c) synthesis methodologies for $Co_{SA}-N_2O_1/MXene$, reprinted with permission from [83].
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Fig. 2. Characterization of Pt-V morphologically in the STEM image of Pt-V₂CT_x nanosheets. (a) Low-magnification STEM images of the Pt-V nanosheets TEM image; (b) High-magnification of STEM image of Pt-V₂CT_x, (c) The TEM-EDS mapping image of Pt-V₂CT_x; (d) THE Pt-V₂CT_x nanosheets HAADF-STEM image; (e) The line-scanning intensity profile in rectangular region 1 and 2 in b; (f-h) DFT simulation for the origin of catalytic activity of atomic structure of V₂C-O₂. Reprinted with permission from [78].

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2228 **Fig. 3.** (a) Schematic illustration of $\text{Cu}_{\text{SA}}\text{/B-MXene}$, reprinted with permission from [81]; (b)
 2229 synthesis pathway for $\text{Ru}_{\text{SA}}\text{-N-S-Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$: $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ is derived from the MAX phase using a LiF/HCl
 2230 etchant, followed by N, S, and Ru single-atom doping through a freeze-drying process and thermal
 2231 annealing under an argon atmosphere, reprinted with permission from [82]; (c) synthesis procedure
 2232 of Alk-MXene/FePc catalyst, reprinted with permission from [84].
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2235 **Fig. 4.** (a) Schematic representation of the fabrication of $\text{Co}_{\text{SA}}@MXene$ composites using V_2CT_x
 2236 as an example, reprinted with permission from [85]; (b) anchoring of L-tryptophan onto the surface
 2237 of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene followed by the synthesis of dual-atom $\text{CoNiTi}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ composites, reprinted with
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 2239 atmosphere, Reprinted with permission from [87].
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2253 **Fig. 6.** Morphological characteristics of the $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x\text{-Pt}_{\text{SA}}$ catalyst. (a) TEM image of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$; (b)
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 2280 (g) wavelet transform of Cu foil, CuO, $\text{Cu}_{\text{SA}}/\text{MXene}$, and $\text{Cu}_{\text{SA}}/\text{B-MXene-4}$. Reprinted with
 2281 permission from [81].

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 2352 Reprinted with permission from [107].
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 2378 (g) The degradation efficiency of SMX in the CrN₄/MXene system in different actual wastewater.
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2407 **Fig. 24.** DFT calculation: (a) adsorption energies of H^* on Nb_2C , $\text{Fe}_{0.1}/\text{Nb}_2\text{C}$, $\text{Cu}_{0.2}/\text{Nb}_2\text{C}$, and
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 2409 illustration of the d-band center relative to the Fermi level, showing reduced H^* -metal interaction;
 2410 (d) optimized structures for H^* and H_2 adsorption, including the transition state for H^* conversion
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 2412 $\text{Cu}_{0.2}/\text{Fe}_{0.1}/\text{Nb}_2\text{C}$, where the yellow and cyan regions represent electron accumulation and
 2413 depletion, respectively. Reprinted with permission from [135].

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 2417 (b) The charge-density variation during PMS activation on CoSA-N₄ and CoSA-N₂O₁/MXene with
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 2419 density of states (PDOS) of Co in CoSA-N₄ and CoSA-N₂O₁/MXene; (e) schematic diagram
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 2421 energy profiles depicting ¹O₂ formation for the CoSA-N₄/PMS and CoSA-N₂O₁/PMS systems.
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 2426 permission from [136].

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 2438 BPNN-GA's fitness curve for each generation; (c) Fitting between experimental data and BPNN-
 2439 GA predicted data; (d) Fitness curve of RF-GA model. Reproduced with the permission from
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 2444 calculate the adsorption energy of molecularly adsorbed intermediates, guiding the formulation of
 2445 a valence-electron matching law. Second, the electronic structure was investigated to elucidate the
 2446 adsorption mechanism. Finally, the ML descriptors were created to assist catalyst design. Feature
 2447 engineering and the SISSO algorithm for predicting R^2 ; (b) Correlation of features after feature
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 2450 Structure doping elements, M-Ti₂C, M-Ti₂CO₂ structural diagrams, adsorbed atom and molecular
 2451 schematics; (e) Formation energy data for the two structures. Reprinted with permission from
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2455 Fig. 30 (a) E_{ads} trends of 3d, 4d, and 5d TMs on M_2C (top three rows) and M_2N (bottom three
 2456 rows) MXenes; (b) Parity map in eV between the DFT-calculated E_b vs. ML RFR predicted E_b . (c)
 2457 Parity plot of the entire dataset between the DFT-calculated E_{ads} distinguishing X; (d) The SA TM
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 2464 Linear relationship between actual values and COL-FCANN predictions of COTA. (d) Train and
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2467 true values vs FLU-FCANN prediction levels; (g) Fluctuations of true values vs FLU-FCANN
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 2479 structure; (b) transport of water, PMS, and BPA through nanochannels with widths of 1.37, 5, and
 2480 10 nm at 0, 10, and 20 ns; (c) comparison of the mean square displacement (MSD) of PMS
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2492 **Fig. 35.** (a) AlpMD snapshots of V_2CO_2 H_2O systems with 10 H_2O , 20 H_2O , and 30 H_2O . Local
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2500 **Fig. 36.** (a) The initial snapshot of the simulated box for the MXOH@ZIF-MO system. Water
2501 molecules were depicted using “QuickSurf” VMD models. Final close snapshot from the studied
2502 simulation boxes for CIP; (b) MO; (c) pollutant molecules. Reprinted with permission from [149].

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2508 **Fig. 37.** Key future prospects of SACs@MXene catalyst (Figure was created with BioRender.com).

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2511 **List of Tables**2512 **Table 1.** Toxic effects of selected organic compounds.

Compound	Category	Human health effects	Environmental effects
Sulfamethoxazole	Pharmaceutical (antibiotic)	Allergic reactions, liver/kidney toxicity, and promotes antibiotic resistance	Persistent in water, toxic to algae/invertebrates, spreads resistance genes
Sulfadimidine	Pharmaceutical (antibiotic)	Endocrine disruption, allergic responses, and antibiotic resistance	Stable in soil/water, toxic to aquatic organisms, promotes resistance genes
Bisphenol A (BPA)	Endocrine disruptor / plastic monomer	Estrogen mimic, infertility, obesity, cancer risk	Persistent in waters/sediments, reproductive toxicity in fish/amphibians
Acetaminophen	Pharmaceutical (analgesic)	Liver and kidney toxicity at high doses, metabolic impairment	Found in wastewater, toxic to algae/fish, induces oxidative stress
Carbamazepine	Pharmaceutical (antiepileptic)	Neurological side effects, long persistence in the body	Extremely persistent, bioaccumulates, affects fish reproduction
2,4-Dichlorophenol	Industrial chemical/pesticide intermediate	Irritant, liver/kidney toxicity, possible carcinogen	Toxic to aquatic organisms, oxidative stress, and bioaccumulation
Pb-EDTA	Heavy metal-organic complex	Lead neurotoxicity (brain damage in children), kidney damage	Mobile in water/soil, enhances heavy-metal pollution
Ranitidine	Pharmaceutical (antacid)	Carcinogenic NDMA impurity risk, liver stress	Persistent in water, toxic to aquatic organisms
Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF)	Polymer / microplastic source	Generally stable; microplastics cause inflammation and oxidative stress	Persistent microplastics, sediment accumulation, and ingestion harm aquatic life

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2514 **Table 2.** Summary of the synthesis methods of various SAs@MXene catalysts.

MXene precursor	Type of single atom	Synthesis method	Parameters	Anchoring mechanism	Final product	Ref.
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Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	Pt	Rapid thermal shock under H ₂ atmosphere	400 °C, 10 min, 10 % H ₂ /Ar	Pt atoms anchored to oxygen vacancies, forming Pt-Ti bonds	Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x -Pt _{SA}	[77]
V ₂ CT _x	Pt	Self-reduction via V ₂ CT _x vacancies	Room temperature, 6 h	Substitutional Pt at V vacancies forming Pt-C bonds	Pt-V ₂ CT _x MXene nanosheets	[78]
Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	Ru	Coordination-assisted method using melamine and RuCl ₃	550 °C, 2 h, Ar	Strong Ru-N coordination bonds (N-doped MXene)	Ru _{SA} -N-Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	[80]
Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	Cu	One-step calcination	600 °C, 2 h, Ar	Cu-O ₂ B coordination	Cu-SA/B-MXene-4	[81]
Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	Ru	Freeze-drying	500 °C, 2 h, Ar	Heteroatom-mediated Ru-N and Ru-S coordination	Ru _{SA} -N-S-Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	[82]
Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	Co	Coordination-assisted pyrolysis	550 °C, 2 h	The Co atoms coordinate with nitrogen atoms	Co _{SA} -N ₂ O ₁ /MXene	[83]
Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	Fe	Self-assembly of FePc with Alk-MXene via ultrasonic treatment	Sonicated for 30 min and then stirred for 20 h	Axial O-ligand coordination forming Fe-N ₄ O ₁	Alk-MXene/FePc with Fe-N ₄ O ₁	[84]
V ₂ CT _x , Nb ₂ CT _x , Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	Co	Iced photochemical reduction method	0 °C, UV light (254 nm, 10 W), 1 h	Photochemical reduction-controlled atom anchoring	Co@V ₂ CT _x , Co@Nb ₂ CT _x , Co@Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	[85]
Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	Co and Ni	L-tryptophan functionalization + UV-assisted dual metal photoreduction	0 °C, UV light (254 nm, 10 W), 2h	Metal-N/O coordination via tryptophan	Co-Ni-Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	[86]
Nb ₂ C	Pt	Chemical exfoliation and single-atom loading	400 °C, 15 min, 10 % H ₂ /Ar	Pt(VI) ions are partially reduced by Nb surface atoms around vacancies	Pt-Nb ₂ C	[87]
Mo ₂ TiC ₂ T _x	Pt	In situ electrochemical exfoliation and atomic Pt deposition	-	Pt atoms occupy Mo vacancies	Mo ₂ TiC ₂ T _x -Pt _{SA}	[88]

$Ti_3C_2T_x$	Ru	Wet-chemistry impregnation	Stirring, 18h	Ru-O coordination on $Ti_3C_2T_x$ surface	$Ru_{SA}@Ti_3C_2T_x$	[89]
Nb_2CT_x	Pt	Coprecipitation	Vacuum drying at 60 °C for 10 h	Pt is coordinated with the surrounding C atoms on the MXene	SA Pt- Nb_2CT_x	[91]

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2527 **Table 3.** Scalability assessment of various synthesis strategies for SAs@MXenes catalyst.

Synthesis method	Scalability level	Reason for scalability assessment	Industrial feasibility	Ref.
Defect engineering	Moderately scalable	Industrial furnaces are available, but high energy consumption and a controlled atmosphere increase cost	Possible but energy-intensive	[77]
UV-mediated photochemical synthesis	Limited to moderately	Light penetration and uniform irradiation become	Requires specialized	[85]

		challenging at large volumes	photoreactor systems	
Pyrolysis/ Heteroatom coordination	Highly scalable	Uses conventional furnace annealing, bulk powder processing possible, straightforward precursor chemistry	Suitable for industrial-scale fabrication	[80]
Electrochemical deposition	Moderately scalable	Requires reactor engineering, electrode design, and controlled current distribution for scale-up	Feasible with engineering optimization	[88]
Wet chemistry/ impregnation	Highly scalable	Simple solution mixing, no vacuum system, low equipment cost	Very suitable for large-scale production	[89]
Atomic layer deposition	Low scalability for bulk production	Vacuum-based, slow deposition rate, high equipment and operational cost	Suitable mainly for precision or small-scale production	[108]

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2529 **Table 4.** Limitations of the characterization techniques generally used for single-atom studies.

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Characterization Technique	Limitations
HAADF-STEM	An electron beam may damage MXene layers or cause atomic migration/aggregation. Low contrast when the atomic number difference between single atoms and MXene elements is small. Difficulty distinguishing surface and subsurface atoms in layered MXenes.
XANES/EXAFS	Requires synchrotron facilities, limiting accessibility. Interpretation depends heavily on reference standards and simulations. Lacks spatial resolution to identify exact atom positions on MXene surfaces. Difficult to differentiate neighboring light atoms (C, N, O) in MXene terminations. Low metal loading leads to weak signals and a poor signal-to-noise ratio.
EPR	Some signals disappear at room temperature and require low-temperature analysis, which adds experimental complexity. It provides limited structural information and sensitivity limitations. Cannot detect diamagnetic species. This makes EPR incomplete for SACs characterization.
Raman spectroscopy	Weak or broad Raman signals due to MXene disorder and surface terminations. Insensitive to isolated single atoms, mainly probes lattice vibrations. Laser heating can oxidize or damage MXene surfaces.

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2533 **Table 5.** Summary of SAs@MXene composites for the degradation and treatment of organic
 2534 pollutants.
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MXene catalysts	Target molecule (s)	Active site (single atom)	Operating conditions	Performance	Mechanism	Ref.
CrN ₄ /MXene	Sulfamethoxazole (SMX), Bisphenol A (BPA), Sulfadimidine (SDZ), Ciprofloxacin, 4-Nitrophenol	Cr	RT, pH 6.8	98% removal	Selective electrocatalytic ¹ O ₂ production via end-on O ₂ adsorption	[97]
Co _{SA} -N-Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	Acetaminophen (ACE)	Co	pH 6.8, PMS = 0.7 mM	100% ACE removal in 3 min	Selective ·O ₂ ⁻ -dominated radical pathway via PMS activation	[98]
Co@Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x (Co-MXene)	Carbamazepine (CBZ, Ibuprofen, Bisphenol A, Sulfamethoxazole)	Co	RT + PMS	100% CBZ degradation in 240 ms	Generation of ¹ O ₂ and high valent Co-Oxo, ROS-mediated oxidation	[102]
Fe-SA/Mo ₂ TiC ₂ T _x	Sulfamethoxazole	Fe	RT, 2.0 V	100% degradation in <2s	Electrocatalytic PMS activation	[103]
Cu-SA/MXene	BPA	Cu	RT, pH 3-11, PMS	100% BPA degradation in 10 min	PMS activation (nonradical oxidation)	[104]
Co-N-Ti _{3-x} C ₂ T _y membrane	Ranitidine	Co	PMS = 0.15 mM T = 298 K	100% ranitidine degradation	Nano-confined Co-N ₁ C ₂ /PMS-mediated oxidation for high-efficiency OMP degradation	[105]
Co-SA/MXene	Ranitidine (RAN)	Co	RT, pH 7, PMS = 50 mg/L	100% removal	PMS activation (Catalytic Oxidation)	[106]
Co _{SA} /MCSMx MXene	Bisphenol A (BPA)	Co	pH 3.5, PMS = 0.2 g/L	100% BPA removal	Non-radical electron	[107]

					transfer process (ETP)	
C-Cu-MXene, F-Cu-MXene	Sulfamethoxazole (SMX)	Cu	pH 7.4, PMS=1.2 mmol/L	95% removal over 5 cycles	Dominant reactive species confirmed via EPR, radical scavengers	[108]
Co@MXene	Pb-EDTA (Ethylene Diamine Tetra Acetic Acid)	Co	pH 3-9, PMS= 1 mM	93.6% Pb-EDTA removal	Generation of Co(IV), single-atom Co radical 1O_2 formation	[109]
Co@Ti _{2-x} N	Carbamazepine (CBZ), SMX, 2,4-dichlorophenol (2,4-DCP)	Co	pH 3-11, 25 °C, PMS= 2 mM	Complete degradation of CBZ, SMX, and 2,4-DCP	PMS activation (nonradical oxidation)	[110]

2536 RT= Room Temperature

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2557 **Table 6.** Comparative evaluation of the catalytic performance of SAs@MXenes versus other

2558 SAC supports and conventional catalysts in organic pollutant degradation.

Catalyst Type	Organic pollutant	Rate constant, k (min ⁻¹)	Turn over frequency (TOF) (min ⁻¹)	Metal leaching (μg L ⁻¹)	Stability/Cycles	Efficiency	Ref.

CrN ₄ /MXene	Sulfamethoxazole	0.097	1.79	<6	6 cycles	95% degradation	[97]
Co _{SA} -N-Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	Acetaminophen	1.011	39 times and 816 times higher than homogeneous catalysts	<10	4 cycles	100% degradation	[98]
Co _{SA} -NC/H ₂ O/MX	Bisphenol A	1.32	-	0.07 mg L ⁻¹	3 cycles	100% degradation	[101]
Co single-atom embedded MXene membrane	Carbamazepine	0.2924	2.73	<3.18	4 cycles	100% degradation	[102]
Fe-SA/Mo ₂ TiC ₂ T _x	Sulfamethoxazole	2.89	Much higher than Fe nanoparticle (>10 ⁴ times)	<0.01 mg L ⁻¹	5 cycles	100% degradation	[103]
Cu-SA/MXene-900	Bisphenol A	0.6117	4.71 × 10 ⁻²	0.08-0.68	5 cycles	100% degradation	[104]
CoSA/MCS Mx	Bisphenol A	0.536	-	0.018	2 cycles	100% removal	[107]
C-Cu-MXene	Sulfamethoxazole	0.0485	-	-	5 cycles	100% degradation	[108]
MXene/Cu-G-CN	Ciprofloxacin, norfloxacin	0.68	3.13 × 10 ²	No metal content leached	7 cycles	88.76 % and 91 % degradation	[111]
SA-Zn/rGO	Sulfamethoxazole	2.28	-	-	5 cycles	92% removal	[112]
Fe _{SA} -N-CNT	Bisphenol A	256 μmol s ⁻¹ g ⁻¹	-	Undetectable	-	Complete degradation	[113]
Fe ₁ -M15 (single-atom Fe-N ₄ on N-doped carbon)	Bisphenol A	8.4	-	0.391 ppm	-	22 ppm degradation within 40 sec	[114]
Co _{SAC} -NG (single-atom Co on N-	Bisphenol A	4.42 × 10 ⁻²	-	0.008 mg L ⁻¹	4 cycles	99.70 % degradation	[115]

doped graphene)							
SAFe-MCN (single-atom Fe dispersed g-C ₃ N ₄)	Sulfamethoxazole	0.602	5.27	2.55	5 cycles	98% degradation	[116]
Fe-SA200@CN	Bisphenol A	0.231	-	0.24 mg L ⁻¹	3 cycles	95 % degradation	[117]
W-SA-g-C ₃ N ₄ -22.5	Sulfamethazine	0.0267	-	-	4 cycles	80 % degradation	[118]
Fe@MesoC	Sulfamethoxazole	-	-	0.06-0.68 mg L ⁻¹	3 cycles	100 % removal	[119]
MnSiO _x /Fe@C	Sulfamethoxazole	0.0583	-	<0.035 mg L ⁻¹	4 cycles	100% removal	[120]
2.4%Pd-BiVO ₄	Sulfamethoxazole	0.01985	-	-	5 cycles	99% removal	[121]
MIL-100@ZIF-67@MXene	Carbamazepine	0.16	-	Fe= 5, Co=1, and Ti = 1	6 cycles	95% degradation	[122]
MCoO@Co-N-C	Bisphenol A	0.472	8.64	0.026 mg L ⁻¹	3 cycles	98% degradation	[123]
MZPC-9 (N, S co-doped carbon encapsulated Co ₂ P on MXene)	Bisphenol A	1.485	29.7	0.084 ppm	-	98.2% degradation	[124]
Sandwich like Co ₃ O ₄ /MXene composite	Bisphenol A	0.3984	-	<0.4 mg L ⁻¹	5 cycles	95% degradation	[125]
NMS@MX (Ni _x Mg _{4-x} S ₄ sulfide intercalated MXene)	Bisphenol A	0.049	-	-	4 cycles	92% degradation	[126]

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Table 7. Comparison of ML models for pollutant degradation applications.

ML method	Formula	Strengths for SAs@MXenes	DFT data to be integrated
Linear regression (LR)	$\hat{y} = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i x_i$	Baseline model; interpretable, good for small descriptor sets (atomic radius, electronegativity, adsorption energy)	Adsorption energies Eads, formation energy of SAC, charge density difference, bond lengths.
Support vector regression (SVR)	$\hat{y}(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N (\alpha_i - \alpha_i^*) K(x_i - x) + b$	Captures non-linear trends; effective with limited data	DFT adsorption barriers like pollutant-SAC interaction, HOMO-LUMO gaps, Bader charges
Random forest (RF)	$\hat{y} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T f_t(x)$ (ensemble of decision trees)	Robust, handles mixed descriptors (electronic + geometric), feature importance ranking	Adsorption energy set Eads, vacancy formation energy, DOS features
Gradient boosting (XGBoost)	Additive model: $\hat{y}_m(x) = \hat{y}_{m-1}(x) + \eta f_m(x)$	High accuracy, works with limited DFT datasets, interpretable with SHAP values	Adsorption energies, reaction barriers from CI-NEB, oxidation state changes of active sites
Gaussian process regression (GPR)	$\hat{y}(x) \sim \text{GP}(m(x), k(x, x'))$	Gives uncertainty estimates good for active learning loops	DFT-calculated adsorption energies of pollutants, work function, charge transfer data
Artificial neural networks (ANN)	$\hat{y} = f(W_2 \cdot \sigma(W_1 x + b_1) + b_2)$	Learns complex non-linear interactions, scalable to large datasets, adaptable to diverse descriptors	DFT adsorption barriers, electronic DOS, charge density maps, cohesive energies
Graph neural networks (GNNs: SchNet, MEGNet, DimeNet)	Message-passing: $h_i^{(k+1)} = \Phi(h_i^{(k)}, \sum_{j \in N(i)} \Psi(h_i^{(k)}, h_j^{(k)}, e_{ij}))$	Best for atomic-scale data, directly uses atomic graphs from DFT structures, predicts adsorption,	DFT-relaxed structures (atomic coordinates), total energies, charge densities

		activation barriers without hand-crafted features	
Active Learning (with Bayesian optimization)	Iteratively train ML → propose candidates → DFT validate → retrain. Acquisition function: $a(x) = \mu(x) + \kappa\sigma(x)$	Efficiently explores huge SAC search space, reduces costly DFT runs	Any DFT label, adsorption energies, NEB barriers, pollutant-SAC binding geometries

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Table 8. Comparison of ML models and associated organic pollutants for degradation studies.

Pollutant	Relevant degradation pathway (SAs@MXene)	Key DFT descriptors to use	Recommended ML models	Rationale
Sulfamethoxazole (SMX)	Persulfate activation by SACs → generates $\cdot\text{OH}$, $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$, $^1\text{O}_2$. Adsorption on Cu/Ti sites critical	Adsorption energy of SMX on SAC (E ads) Bond dissociation energy of S-N bond. Charge transfer (Bader).	SVR/Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) with SHAP interpretability	Non-linear but small dataset, interpretability is important to connect electronic descriptors to SMX degradation

		PS activation energy		
Bisphenol-A (BPA)	PMS or PDS activation, oxidative radical degradation. Electron transfer efficiency at SAC site dominates	Adsorption energy of BPA aromatic ring on MXene. Work function changes. HOMO-LUMO gap alignment O vacancy formation energy	Random Forest/ ANN (MLP)	BPA is bulky, multiple adsorption sites, tree ensembles capture mixed descriptors; ANN useful if dataset > 200 points
Acetaminophen (ACT/APAP)	Hydroxyl radical attack on aromatic ring or amide group. Photocatalysis dominant (band gap alignment)	Adsorption energy of APAP. Band gap (PBE + HSE06 correction). Exciton binding energy. Electron density difference at amide group.	GPR + Active Learning	Useful for small datasets, uncertainty guides new DFT runs, balances electronic + adsorption features
Carbamazepine (CBZ)	Stable aromatic pollutant requires strong oxidant activation. Adsorption is weak, so SAC choice is critical	Adsorption energy of CBZ at SAC site. NEB barrier for C-N bond scission π - π stacking stabilization energy. Solvation effect (implicit solvation)	GNN (SchNet/MEGNet)	Complex aromatic, large molecule, graph models better capture molecular complexity and adsorption geometries.
Ranitidine (RAN)	Photocatalytic degradation (visible light) \rightarrow NDMA formation risk. Need to balance degradation vs. byproduct suppression	Adsorption energy on MXene. Band gap & DOS (HSE06). Charge transfer to the nitro group. Reaction pathway barrier to NDMA intermediates (NEB)	XGBoost + Multi objective Optimization	Can optimize two objectives: maximize degradation rate, minimize NDMA formation potential.

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